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Covalent functionalization of 1D and 2D sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes – twelve years of progress (2011–2023)

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Abstract

Carbon nanoallotropes have attracted significant attention in the field of materials science due to their unique combination of physicochemical and biological properties, with numerous applications. One-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes, such as carbon nanohorns (CNHs), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and graphene, have emerged as prominent candidates for a variety of technological advancements. To fully exploit their exceptional characteristics, the covalent functionalization of these nanostructures may alleviate the problems with processing and the final performance. This route of the carbon nanoallotrope functionalization is based on a covalent attachment of functional groups or molecules (*via* linkers of various strengths) to their surfaces, enabling precise control over physical, chemical, biological, and electronic properties. Such an approach opens up new avenues for tailoring the nanoallotrope characteristics, such as solubility/dispersibility, reactivity, and interactions with other materials. Over more than the last decade, significant progress has been made in the covalent functionalization of both 1D and 2D sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes, paving the way for diverse applications in nanoelectronics, energy storage, sensing, and biomedical fields. In this comprehensive review, we provide state-of-the-art advancements and achievements in the covalent functionalization of 1D and 2D sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes during the past dozen years. We aim to highlight the key strategies, methodologies, and breakthroughs that have significantly contributed to this field. Eventually, we discuss the implications of those advancements and explore the opportunities for future research and applications.

Keywords carbon nanohorns (CNHs), carbon nanotubes (CNTs), graphene, graphene oxide, covalent functionalization

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Review of application-oriented covalent modifications of 1D & 2D carbon nanoallotropes, covering years 2011–2023: from functionalization to functionality.

1 Introduction

The discovery of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and graphene has ignited a revolution in materials science, along with the opening of new avenues for the development of next-generation technologies.¹ Up to now, a multitude of one-dimensional (1D) and two-dimensional (2D) carbon nanoallotropes, including carbon nanohorns (CNHs), CNTs, carbon nanofibers (CNFs), graphene, and (reduced) graphene oxide ((r-)GO) have been studied for their excellent physical and chemical properties.² High mechanical strength, thermal stability, specific surface area, and electrical/thermal conductivity, particularly spectacular (and reserved mostly) for the pristine, individual nanoparticles (NPs), made carbon nanoallotropes extremely desirable for a variety of applications, including electronics,³ energy storage,⁴ and biosensing.⁵ Nevertheless, surface functionalization is frequently crucial or even inevitable to mitigate the limitations of realizing the full potential of carbon nanoallotropes.⁶ Hence, in the last dozen years, two functionalization routes, representing concomitantly developed covalent and non-covalent functionalization, were extensively studied.⁷ As compared to the non-covalent functionalization routes such as adsorption or encapsulation (endohedral functionalization), covalent functionalization is considered robust and long-lasting, while facilitating the introduction of a wide range of functional groups. The newly-coming functionalities can be customized to tailor the target-specific properties.⁸

Covalent functionalization of carbon nanoallotropes generally covers radical, electrophilic, and nucleophilic addition as well as cycloaddition. Radical additions are triggered by the external stimuli such as radical initiators, heat or irradiation, enabling anchoring of radical species to the carbon nanoallotrope surface.⁹ Electrophilic and nucleophilic addition involve the addition of the respective species, such as *in situ* generated ions, yielding new C-C or C-X bonds (where X = heteroatom), while cycloaddition leads to ring formations on the nanocarbon surface.¹⁰

The covalent functionalization of 1D and 2D sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes impacts their mechanical strength, thermal stability, thermal and electrical conductivity, and biocompatibility. Moreover, improvements in nanoallotrope solubility, hydrophilicity, and chemical stability were frequently predesigned and further verified experimentally. Here, we present a systematic overview of dozen years of covalent functionalization of 1D and 2D sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes. This more-than-a-decade period has witnessed a significant progress in the development of new functionalization methods for carbon nanoallotropes, along with the discovery of exciting properties and applications of novel nanomaterials. Indeed, a few reviews focused on chemical modifications of nanocarbons,^{11,12} yet none, since 2011, has comprehensively reviewed covalent functionalization across sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes. **Figure 1** is the account of studies published from 2011 to 2023 with the data acquired from *Google Scholar* and *Web of Science*, using the following keywords: ‘functionalization of carbon nanotubes’, ‘functionalization of carbon nanofibers’, ‘functionalization of carbon nanohorns’, and ‘functionalization of graphene’.

Figure 1 (A) *Google Scholar*, and (B) *Web of Science* data for studies published from 2011-2023. The keywords used were: ‘functionalization of carbon nanotubes’, ‘functionalization of carbon nanofibers’, ‘functionalization of carbon nanohorns’, and ‘functionalization of graphene’.

Our review focuses on new routes for the application-oriented covalent functionalization of carbon nanoallotropes. Those scenarios include radical, electrophilic, and nucleophilic addition, as well as (2+1)-, (2+2)-, (3+2)-, and (4+2)-cycloaddition (according to IUPAC, round bracket corresponds to a number of atoms forming the new ring), with an impact on the final properties of the modified carbon nanoallotropes and, hence, applications (**Figure 2**). The covalent modifications, visualized by model molecular transformations (**Figure 2a**), leading to the most expected applications and functionalities were depicted in **Figure 2b**. We present hereby a comprehensive overview of the key developments, important trends, and the future directions in this area, indicating the most up-to-date perspectives of applications of the covalently functionalized sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes.

Figure 2 The main routes of covalent functionalization of 1D and 2D carbon nanoallotropes; ‘A’ stems for C-, N-, and O-atoms, while ‘X’, ‘Y’, and ‘Z’ correspond, in a general way, to C-, N-, and O-atoms (and their isoelectronic analogues), with R^{1-3} belonging to a variety of dangling moieties. Specifically, for instance, 1,3-dipoles encompass allyl-type (*N*-centered and *O*-centered) and propargyl-allenyl-type (nitrilium and diazonium betaines) structures.

2 Carbon nanohorns (CNHs)

CNHs are conical carbon nanoallotropes of a typical diameter of 2–5 nm and 40–50 nm in length while the overall nomenclature of CNHs can be sometimes misleading. Free-standing, individual conical carbon NPs are most often called ‘nanocones’, while rather their clusters are termed ‘nanohorns’, i.e., CNHs. A rarely used term ‘buckycone’ was introduced by Klein for the nanocones consisting solely of pentagons and hexagons.¹³ Martinez *et al.* attempted to standardize the nomenclature of those carbon nanoforms. According to those recommendations, individual conical carbon nanoallotropes should be termed nanocones, while their aggregates should be called ‘spherical clustered carbon nanocones’.¹⁴ Here, for the sake of clarity, CNHs are synonymous to ‘carbon nanocones’.

CNHs can be traced back to the 1950s, when they were first observed and initially perceived as a specific rearrangement of graphite flakes.¹⁵ The conical structure of CNHs was hypothesized more than 40 years later¹⁶ with the first synthesis of multi-walled CNHs (reported in the same year) performed by vapor condensation under ultrahigh vacuum.¹⁷ Three years later, in order to understand disclination defects in curved carbon nanostructures, Krishnan *et al.* produced CNHs *via* pyrolysis of hydrocarbons.¹⁸ The process, called the Kvaerner plasma torch method, is known to produce flat discs, soot, and multi-walled CNHs in large quantities.

CNHs are similar in chemical properties to single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs). However, unlike small fullerenes, their cage cavity is accessible *via* a progressive oxidation.¹⁹ The similarity to CNTs made them potential candidates to serve multiple purposes, including drug delivery, biomedical applications,²⁰ sensors,²¹ gas storage,²² etc. CNHs can be synthesized in large quantities at room temperature in the absence of metal catalysts, which gives them an edge over CNTs. The use of metal catalysts during the synthesis of CNTs might impose an additional step of

strong acid, plasma, or vacuum treatment, which, along with the removal of metal particles, might introduce defects in graphitic structure and induce the loss of carbon material.²³ At the same time, this characteristic allows for less complex studies of structure, properties, and applications of a CNHs as a graphene family representative.

Pristine CNHs are known for their enhanced field-emission, semiconduction, thermal stability, and oxidation resistance properties. However, there are reasons substantially restricting the research and development of CNHs. For instance, the reason for only a very few computational studies on CNHs is their low symmetry of CNHs. This morphological parameter significantly complicates quantum modeling. Moreover, realistically portrayed not only CNHs but also graphene, fullerenes, and CNTs, consist of a varying number of pentagons, hexagons, and heptagons. Additionally, a still limited number of the experimental findings can be explained based on difficult dispersibility, separation, and thus individual CNH functionalization, as CNHs, during the synthesis, form chemically bonded clusters of up to 100 nm in diameter.²⁴

Concerning characteristics, pristine CNHs show two bands in the Raman spectra: the G-band at 1593 cm^{-1} and the D-band at 1341 cm^{-1} . The G-band corresponds to the vibrations of carbon atoms, like the E_{2g} vibrations, while the D-band corresponds to the A_{1g} symmetry or a basal symmetry loss of structure. The electronic properties of CNHs, in their idealistic symmetrical geometry, are governed by their conical structure with an optional electron transfer to the CNH tip. Due to the unique mechanical properties among the nanocarbon family, CNHs were proposed as a material of choice for nanoindentation and atomic force microscopy (AFM).²⁵ This paradigm stemmed from the fact that mechanical force, applied to the tip, was accompanied by a simultaneous holding of the cone base. On the other hand, CNHs might undergo tip-to-base cone

inversion, while this phenomenon would be inhibited by an increased number of tip pentagons, hence, the overall rigidity.

Porosity and the ability to expose the internal cavity of CNHs *via* oxidation make them a potential candidate for the storage of fluids. Heat treatment of CNHs under oxidative or acidic conditions leads to the formation of holes (called also ‘nanogates’ or ‘nanowindows’) in the CNH skeleton. The holes open the internal structure, and, hence, an increase in surface area to $1300 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and pore volume to 0.9 mL g^{-1} is observed. Contrarily, ‘sewing’ of the so-generated holes depends upon their location as well as the nanowindow size, i.e., side-wall holes, and the holes larger than 0.9 nm are difficult to close. Generally, chemical treatment serves the dual purpose of opening holes as well as making the addition of functional groups possible for CNHs. The removal of added functional groups from the CNHs is possible at higher temperatures in the presence of hydrogen, which is true also for the other sp^2 -carbon nanoallotropes.

The semiconduction of pristine CNHs is influenced by the adsorption of CO_2 and O_2 . Micropores of 0.11 mL g^{-1} and a surface area of $308 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ were observed while studying the porosity of CNHs *via* nitrogen adsorption.²⁶ The observed micropores are classified as temperature-dependent interstitial pores and consistent nanoscale internal pores. An increase in the CNH microporosity was observed upon high-pressure compression. Recently, a new method of CNH opening was proposed based on a hydrothermal reaction with H_2O_2 .²⁷ Depending on the applied conditions, the new GO forms could be formed with potential applications in electrochemistry, and/or in the creation of new omniphobic and translucent surfaces.²⁸ The studies related to the covalent functionalization of CNHs are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table 1 Covalent functionalization of CNHs

Reactants	<i>In situ</i> produced reagent	Mechanism	Degree of functionalization	Application	Ref.
CNHs and arylamine	-----	Radical addition	-----	Capturing zinc tetraphenyl porphyrin (ZnTPP)	Kamei <i>et al.</i> 2020 ²⁹
CNHs and azides	Nitrene	(2+1)-Nitrene cycloaddition	One organic unit per 58-112 carbon atoms	Immobilization of Au NPs	Karousis <i>et al.</i> 2011 ³⁰
Aryl functionalized CNHs and fulleropyrrolidine	Aryl-diazonium salts	Copper-catalyzed alkyne azide cycloaddition	One C ₆₀ unit per 885 carbon atoms	-----	Karousis <i>et al.</i> 2012 ³¹
CNHs, glycine, and aldehydes (3 different)	Azomethine ylides	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	-----	SERS Activity	Iglesias <i>et al.</i> 2020 ³²
Route 1: CNHs and 2-(trimethylsilyl)phenyl triflate. Route 2: CNHs and anthranilic acid	Benzynes	(2+2)- and (4+2)-benzyne cycloaddition	-----	-----	Chronopoulos <i>et al.</i> 2013 ³³
CNHs bearing terminal alkyne subunits and azide bearing C ₆₀	-----	Catalyzed (3+2)-azide-alkyne cycloaddition	-----	Electrochemical properties	Vizuete <i>et al.</i> 2011 ³⁴
CNHs equipped with NH ₃ ⁺ groups and C ₆₀ bearing a crown ether unit	-----	Ammonium /crown ether interactions	One functional group per 110 carbon atoms	Photophysical properties	Vizuete <i>et al.</i> 2014 ³⁵
CNHs and potassium naphthalenide; electrophiles including: CH ₃ , <i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇ , and C ₆ H ₅	-----	Reductive dismantling. the second step is quenching of the reduced CNHs with electrophiles	One substituent per every 55, 202, and 282 carbon atoms for the listed electrophiles, respectively	-----	Voiry <i>et al.</i> 2015 ³⁶
SWCNHs, HNO ₃	-----	Radical surface oxidation	-----	Surfactant-free colloids in water	Agresti <i>et al.</i> 2018 ³⁷
CNHs + O ₂	-----	O ₂ or He plasma treatment	-----	Dispersion and size control of CNHs in water	Lin <i>et al.</i> 2016 ³⁸
Hydrophobic PVDF membranes and CNHs	-----	Nitrogen plasma treatment	-----	Antithrombogenic activity, cytotoxicity and blood platelet adhesion, implants	Zieba <i>et al.</i> 2022 ³⁹

2.1 Radical addition

The structure and reactivity of (macro)molecules can be qualitatively and quantitatively studied *via* single-molecule atomic-resolution real-time electron microscopy (SMAR-TEM).⁴⁰ The principle of this technique represents a ‘chemical fishhook’ strategy, i.e., a capture of molecules from solution and their subsequent electron microscopic studies. For TEM analysis of carboxylic acid derivatives, amino-CNHs were employed as such fishhooks. Capturing inorganic clusters and aromatic molecules *via* this technique is possible due to the formation of metal-oxygen bonds and π - π stacking, respectively. At the same time, H₂N-CNH-based SMAR-TEM can be troublesome as the amide (-CONH-) group bond rotation may lead to flexible addend adsorption on the CNH surface, thereby preventing real-time monitoring of the covalent modifications. Indeed, selective installation of aromatic groups on both positive and negative curvatures of CNHs was possible with the addition of aryl radicals. Such an approach enabled the additive anchoring of the aryl group perpendicular to the CNH surface, eliminating the possibility of physisorption. A reaction of arylamine and isoamyl nitrite in the presence of CNH aggregates, followed by thermal decomposition of the resulting diazonium salts, generated the aryl radicals which were preferentially tethered to the CNH tip (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3 Molecular design of the CNH ‘fishhooks’: (a) illustration of an activated carboxylic acid capture by CNH-NH₂ to capture a biotin derivative; High Resolution-Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-TEM) scalebar: 1 nm. The scalebar for TEM and SEM image is 10 nm and 50 nm, respectively. Reproduced from the study by Gorgoll *et al.*⁴¹ with permission. Copyright 2015 American Chemical Society; (b) Metal organic framework (MOF-5) capture on a carboxylic acid fishhook; scalebar: 1 nm. Reproduced from the study by Xing *et al.*⁴² with permission. Copyright 2019 Nature Publishing Group; (c) illustration of capture of aromatics on an aromatic fishhook; scalebar: 1 nm. Reproduced from the study by Harano *et al.*⁴³ Copyright 2012 Nature Publishing Group; (d) a general scheme of free-radical modification of CNHs with an optional further ‘capture’, and (e) illustration of zinc tetraphenyl porphyrin (ZnTPP) molecules; scalebars: 1 nm. Reproduced from the study by Kamei *et al.*²⁹ with permission. Copyright[®] 2020 The Chemical Society of Japan.

Such an addition of a range of aromatic moieties (substituted carbo- and heteroaromatics) enables capturing molecules from the solution. For instance, owing to its axial symmetry, the addition of a *p*-terphenyl radical to CNHs was found to simplify the functionalization imaging. In the less

symmetrical organic addends, the C–C bond rotation hindered the structural identification. A minor comment in this place is that the low degree of functionalization (molecular weight of the chemically altered CNHs increased by 0.00017%) disabled bulk analytical methods from detecting the aryl addends.

2.2 (2+1)-Cycloaddition

Multiple studies employed microwave irradiation to aid the covalent functionalization of CNHs. For instance, microwave-assisted (2+1)-cycloaddition of nitrenes led to covalent grafting of aziridine-rings onto CNHs, which, in turn, led to composite materials of improved dispersibility.³⁰ The extended endocyclic disulfide bond led to Au nanoparticle (NP) stabilization achievable by condensation of aziridine-ring bearing CNHs with thioctic acid ((*R*)-5-(1,2-dithiolan-3-yl)pentanoic acid).

2.3 (3+2)-Cycloaddition

As hybridization of carbon nanoallotropes may lead to a synergism of properties, CNHs were linked to C₆₀ units.³¹ Hence, CNHs were firstly hydrophilized by a two-step modification involving a radical addition of aryl moieties (from the *in situ* generated diazonium salts) bearing a polar *t*-Boc protected ethylene glycol units, further cleaved to free amines. In parallel, a reaction of sarcosine *t*-butyl ester and formaldehyde with C₆₀ led to (3+2)-cycloaddition of azomethine ylides, followed by *t*-butyl cleavage under acidic conditions, resulting in the synthesis of a fulleropyrrolidine derivative with a free -COOH unit. 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethyl aminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDCI) and 1-hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBT) acted as activators in the condensation of CNH and the C₆₀ resulting in the hybrid material. The degree of functionalization for the aryl species

installed into the CNH and C₆₀-moiety was found as 1 ethylene glycol side chain per 216 carbon atoms and 1 C₆₀ unit per 885 carbon atoms, respectively. Similarly, thermal ring-opening of aziridines bearing electron-withdrawing groups leads to the *in situ* generation of azomethine ylides undergoing (3+2)-cycloaddition to CNHs. This process is complementary to the *in situ* produced azomethine ylides generated on the thermal decarboxylation of immonium salts produced from the condensation of amino acids with aldehydes. For instance, CNHs were grafted with the corresponding linkers using ethyl 1-*N*-dodecylaziridine-2-carboxylate or ethyl 1-(5-hydroxypentyl)aziridine-2-carboxylate allowing a subsequent anchoring of Au NPs.⁴⁴ Functionalization of CNHs with oligothiophene was also achieved *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition. The microwave-assisted reaction of CNHs and the *in situ* generated azomethine ylides involved thermal condensation of an α -aminoacid and an aldehyde of a varying number of thiophene units ranging from one to three. Such a covalent incorporation of the five-membered heterocycles into nanostructures boosted their stability as compared to the non-covalent counterparts which depended solely on π - π stacking interactions.³²

2.4 Microwave-assisted covalent functionalization

Covalent functionalization of CNHs *via* benzyne (2+2)-cycloaddition under microwave irradiation-assisted conditions proved their enhanced reactivity with minimal amounts of solvents required as compared to the conventional wet-chemistry conditions. Benzyne was generated either from anthranilic acid derivatives or 2-(trimethylsilyl)phenyl triflate.³³ In addition, the microwave-assisted reaction of CNHs with 2-amino-5-iodobenzoic acid facilitated further modification of CNHs *via* the Sonogashira coupling of iodo-CNHs with propargyl alcohol (**Figure 4**).

Figure 4 Benzene cycloaddition to CNHs surface (*left*); immobilization of Au NPs onto the thioctic-modified CNHs (*right*). Reproduced from the study by Chronopoulos *et al.*³³ with permission. Copyright 2013 The Royal Society of Chemistry.

The propargyl-functionalized CNHs underwent an esterification reaction with thioctic acid leading to the covalent grafting of 1,2-dithiolane rings conjugable with Au NPs toward hybrid materials. Soluble CNHs-C₆₀ nanohybrids were also generated *via* alkyne-azide cycloaddition in the presence of copper(I) catalyst.³⁴ In a similar study, CNH-NH₃⁺ combined with a crown ether moiety bearing C₆₀ units also generated a nanohybrid of an electron acceptor capability for the solar energy conversion systems.³⁵ Last but not least, potassium naphthalenide-reduced CNHs were capable of quenching electrophiles which yielded material of high individualization of modified CNHs, and hence of prospective biomedical applications.^{36, 37}

On the other hand, plasma-assisted functionalization of CNHs has not been extensively studied. >C=O and -OH functional groups were introduced to the surface of CNHs *via* ozone or helium plasma treatment leading also to a size reduction of the CNH-treated clusters.³⁸ Aqueous dispersions of ozone-treated CNHs were found to remain stable for a few months in comparison

to the water dispersions of helium plasma-treated CNHs which flocculated in a few minutes. Owing to the nature of complex reactions between plasma species and CNHs, the underlying mechanism is not clear. Plasma-assisted functionalization with air, nitrogen, and ammonia was also used for the first time to design hemocompatible poly(vinylidene fluoride)/CNHs (PVDF/CNHs) composites.³⁹

3 Carbon nanotubes (CNTs)

Many years prior to the graphene isolation, CNTs were identified and studied. The phrase ‘*carbon nanotubes*’ is a ‘catch-all’ for a variety of tubular nanostructures that share similar structures and forms. The CNT is imaginarily created by a fusion of edges of the hexagonal lattice of sp^2 -carbon atoms forming a hollow cylindrical tube of a high aspect ratio. Generally, CNTs can be described as rolled-up single, double, or multiple graphene sheets with both ends open or capped to form single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs), double-walled carbon nanotubes (DWCNTs), or multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs). The diameter of several-micrometer-long SWCNTs ranges from 0.4 to 2 nm. CNTs are thought to be among the most anisotropic materials hitherto developed owing to their aspect (length-to-diameter) ratio, frequently surpassing 10,000. Chirality, i.e., the angle between the condensed row of hexagons and the nanotube axis, is another crucial characteristic of CNTs. And so, carbon atoms can be structured in a variety of configurations around the nanotube circumference, with armchair, zigzag, and chiral patterns which correspond to their electrical performance and chemical reactivity.²⁴ Concerning the physicochemical characteristics, water or organic solvents generally cannot disperse CNTs which, due to their prevailing hydrophobic nature and the highly developed surface area, often agglomerate *via* van der Waals forces. One of the important alternatives is to process CNTs (or graphene) as Pickering

emulsions in the systems of hydrophilic and hydrophobic solvents.^{45,46} On the other hand, the troublesome agglomeration of CNTs has launched an immense number of studies on their covalent functionalization.

Like all all-other graphitic structures, CNTs reveal a G-band in the Raman spectra in the range of 1500 to 1600 cm^{-1} , D-band at 1300–1400 cm^{-1} , and a G'-band at 2600 cm^{-1} . Several sp^3 -carbon atoms at the open ends and defect sites are directly related to the I_D/I_G ratio. The low energy radial breathing modes (RBMs), which appear between 150 and 350 cm^{-1} , are the most striking features in the Raman spectra reserved only for SWCNTs, while the RBM frequency is correlated with the SWCNT diameters.

3.1 Electrophilic and nucleophilic addition

Highly reductive Birch reaction conditions limit alkylation, arylation as well as the implementation of carbonyl compounds for the sidewall CNT functionalization. Therefore, liquid ammonia can be replaced by anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (THF) to disperse CNTs, and hence widen their accessibility to structurally different electrophiles. Formation of the corresponding side-wall addition CNT derivatives – synthesized under the modified Birch conditions *via* the reaction of ketones/carboxylic acid derivatives with intermediately charged SWCNTs – was performed and cross-verified.⁴⁷ In another approach, a two-step method involving nucleophilic addition and electrophilic trapping of propargyl bromide to link alkynyl groups to the surface of multiple nanocarbons, including CNTs, was applied. This approach was found to preserve the electrical properties of CNTs to a greater extent than the other documented methods, along with the facilitation of *click* Huisgen reaction *via* the azide-tagged substrates.⁴⁸ Another route enabling a direct link to the heteroatoms, explored for both SWCNTs and MWCNTs, was based on grafting

4,4,5,5-tetramethyl-1,3,2-dioxaborolane (BPin) onto *n*-butyllithium- (*n*-BuLi) modified CNTs. This modification led to functionalized CNTs which can react with multiple nucleophiles in the presence of Cu(II) *via* replacement of BPin groups.⁴⁹ Also, a solvent-free covalent attachment of aromatic amines, including 1-aminopyrene (AP), 2-aminofluorene (AF), and 1,5-diaminonaphthalene (DAN), to fullerenes at 180-250 °C takes place *via* nucleophilic addition and 6,6-pyracylene unit. The mechanism for the amine attachment to MWCNTs is still not clear, while it was presumed to rely on pentagonal, octagonal, and heptagonal defect sites. The only-outer-wall degree of MWCNT functionalization was found to be 5-6 wt.% for AP and 2-3 wt.% for AF, respectively, while, surprisingly, morphological changes in the amine-functionalized MWCNTs reduced their dispersibility in isopropanol.⁵⁰ MWCNTs were functionalized with bromine *via* electrophilic addition and radical reactions, including treatment with *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS), NH₄NO₃/NBS, and Br₂ initiated thermally or photochemically. The functionality contents in the CNT-Br samples spanned from 4 wt.% in the brominated sample under Br₂/UV conditions to 6 and 8 wt.% under the NBS/UV and NBS/NH₄NO₃ conditions, respectively. Various nucleophiles, like RO⁻, RCO₂⁻, CN⁻, etc., could replace bromine atom as a viable leaving group, paving the way for a wider range of functionalities and future applications.⁵¹ Additionally, a hybrid nanocomposite of an improved dispersibility in polar solvents was developed by a reaction between the vinyl moiety from octavinyl-polyhedral oligomeric silsesquioxanes (OV-POSS) and the carboxylic group from MWCNT-COOH.⁵²

Solvent-free covalent attachment of crown ethers, i.e., 4-aminobenzo-15-crown-5 and 4'-aminobenzo-18-crown-6 to MWCNTs *via* nucleophilic addition was found to be facilitated by pentagonal or other defects. The degree of MWCNT functionalization (unsuccessful for C₆₀) at 160-170 °C using the two above-mentioned ether moieties was found to be 15 and 25 wt.%,

respectively.⁵³ Recently, functionalization of SWCNTs has become possible through the nucleophilic addition of the *in situ* produced organometallic reagents. The synergistic effect of benzonitrile, CaH₂, and thioacetic acid demonstrated the applicability of nucleophilic addition of nitrogen-based nucleophiles to both pristine and pre-functionalized SWCNTs, with up to 26 wt.% functionalization levels.⁵⁴ Functionalization of MWCNTs *via* the Stöber reaction, and the subsequent nucleophilic addition, enabled an efficient modification of the commercial epoxy resins. The MWCNT@SiO₂-g-BMI/EP nanocomposite displayed an enhanced thermal conductivity accompanied by electrical insulating properties at a rather low nanofiller loading of ~1.25 wt.%.⁵⁵ Also, CNT-NH₂ can serve itself as a substrate modifiable *via* nucleophilic addition to isocyanates. For example, deposition of magnetic NPs on CNT-NH₂, followed by modification with diverse isocyanates, led to magnetic MWCNTs extracting sulfonamides from milk.⁵⁶

3.2 Radical addition

The Fenton hydroxylation reaction was used to functionalize MWCNTs (diameter from 5 to 50 nm).⁵⁷ This behavior stems from the fact that the unsaturated graphene wall bonds can be attacked by free radicals producing -OH groups covalently linked to the newly sp³-hybridized carbon atoms (with an indicator as reduction of the intensity in the π - π^* shake-up structure in the C1s X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), at the expense of sp²-carbon atoms). Importantly, after the Fenton reaction, MWCNT-OH graphitized at 2600 °C (with no observable surface oxygen and a high degree of structural order) exhibited high levels of surface oxygen, i.e., 21 wt.%. Therefore, hydroxylation seemed to be unrelated to a number of edge sites or dangling bonds in the substrate.

Bergman cyclization was employed for the covalent functionalization of MWCNTs using enediyne compounds. Synthesis of Frechet-type enediyne containing dendrimers, followed by

their reaction with MWCNTs at 206 °C in the presence of *N*-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (NMP), led to the dendrimer-functionalized MWCNTs of enhanced dispersibility in numerous organic/polymer systems.⁵⁸ In turn, arene radical functionalization of SWCNTs was achievable from diazonium salt while followed by a reaction with $\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+\text{OH}^-$ yielding CNT salts of excellent dispersibility.⁵⁹ Similarly, SWCNT reaction with 4-aminobenzoic acid and isoamyl nitrite led to side-wall functionalized, self-assembled SWNCTs conjugable with Ag surfaces.⁶⁰ Similarly, radical grafting of activated-ester-moiety bearing xanthate facilitated the anchoring of bimetallic NPs of 1-2 nm in diameter.⁶¹ Also, MWCNTs were hydroxy methylated (3 wt.%) (MWCNT- CH_2OH) using methanol as a functionalizing agent, employing benzoyl peroxide (BPO).⁶²

Macroradical addition of isotactic polypropylene (iPP) to MWCNTs in the presence of BPO led to the grafting of both iPP macromolecules and benzoyl radicals. iPP-grafted MWCNTs displayed an enhanced dispersibility in iPP compared to the pristine MWCNTs as the already grafted iPP chains facilitated stress transmittance between the corresponding interfaces. A gradual increase in yield strength and Young's modulus was observed with an increase in the functionalized MWCNT content from 0.4 to 2.0 wt.%.⁶³

MWCNT modification *via* radical addition of aniline 2,5-double sulfonic acid diazonium salt, followed by blending with polystyrene (PS) emulsion, led to homogeneous MWCNT-PS mixtures which were further employed for the thermal-assisted fabrication of composite films. PS films doped with 0.1 wt.% of MWCNTs displayed, apart from the improved mechanical strength, an enhanced day-light visibility of red, green, and blue colors of films because of effective scattering and background light absorption by MWCNTs.⁶⁴

Aryl radical addition was also employed in the functionalization of 1,3,5-triazine- and *p*-tolyl pre-functionalized SW- and MWCNTs.⁶⁵ The enhanced water dispersibility and self-assembly in

non-polar solvents *via* DA-AD (donor-acceptor and acceptor-donor) hydrogen bonding were observed only for the 1,3,5-triazine-modified CNTs for which covalent functionalization suppressed the π - π stacking ability of nanotubes. This phenomenon has enabled hydrogen bonding-specific interactions with riboflavin (RBF) toward its efficient sensing.

Ultraviolet (UV)-driven radical cleavage of 4-(chloromethyl)benzoate moieties in the benzyl-type polymer side chains, followed by the addition of pristine MWCNTs, led to the nanocarbon-embedded hybrid materials.⁶⁶ Similarly, UV-irradiation produced polysulfide diradicals which were subsequently bonded to the nanotube walls. NaBH₄ was used to reductively cleave the multi-sulfide bonds, and the product was a thiol-functionalized carbon nanotube (CNT-SH) displaying only a little loss of the CNT π -conjugated framework. Thiolene, thiol-epoxy click chemistry, and thiol-thiol redox reaction – all contributed to the post-functionalization of CNT-SH owing to the versatility of thiol groups demonstrating the qualities of an excellent reinforcement agent for epoxy resins.⁶⁷

Extending applicability of CNTs toward an enhanced flow and fouling resistance, MWCNTs were added to PVDF membranes by atomic transfer radical addition (ATRA).⁶⁸ Adding amine-modified MWCNTs (ethylamine-, octylamine-, and octadecylamine-linkers) increased their dispersibility and hydrophilicity in the innovative PVDF membranes.

3.3 (2+1)-Cycloaddition

Experimental data supported the claim that small-diameter SWCNTs, whether metallic or semiconducting, were more readily (2+1)-cycloaddition-functionalized *via* dichlorocarbene than the large-diameter ones. Upon a considerable level of functionalization, the on-state conductance might be essentially preserved over a wide diameter distribution, while the effective bandgap

differences were observed among differently functionalized SWCNTs. Importantly, with their conductivities mostly conserved, (2+1)-cycloadditions emerged as appropriate for SWCNT functionalization over a wide diameter range.⁶⁹ Also, the metallicity of the originally metallic SWCNTs, functionalized *via* (2+1)-cycloaddition of dichlorocarbene, was found to be conserved proving the hypothesis of sp²-hybridization recovery on the side walls of SWCNTs.⁷⁰ Dichlorocarbene functionalization *via* (2+1)-cycloaddition corresponded to the intensity changes in the Raman G-peak and blue shift in respect to the non-functionalized SWCNTs. However, those Raman signature changes were subtle in the case of monovalent and (3+2)-dipolar cycloaddition functionalization of SWCNTs.⁷¹ Weak intervalley optical phonon scattering and broken side-wall C–C bonds in the (2+1)-cycloaddition functionalized SWCNTs were considered the reasons for a low excitation of the Raman D-band.⁷²

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) contrast agents were covalently anchored onto iron-filled multiwall carbon nanotubes (Fe@MWCNTs). Polyethylene glycol (PEG5000) was applied to oxidized Fe@MWCNTs – either directly through esterification or by the use of acyl chloride derivatives. An aminophenol ligand (Fe@OMWCNT-L) was instead employed to functionalize the latter ones. In addition, *N*-phenyl aziridine groups were added to unmodified Fe@MWCNTs *via* (2+1)-cycloaddition of nitrenes. All of those chemically altered nanotubes functioned as a means of coordinating Fe³⁺ ions.⁷³ In our study comparing cellular uptake and toxicity of pristine *versus* so-modified Fe@MWCNTs against human monocyte macrophages (HMMs) and T47D breast cancer cells, the latter ones were found more cytotoxic to T47D cells than to HMMs. Further modification of Fe@MWCNTs *via* non-covalent loading of 5-fluorouracil or covalent linking of purpurin introduced both an enhanced and selective cytotoxicity as the modified nanotube hybrids were more cytotoxic for T47D cancer cells than HMMs.⁷⁴ Other CNTs, functionalized *via* (2+1)-

cycloaddition of nitrene-based linkers bearing amino groups, and hence, electrostatically interact with DNA, could serve as vectors in gene therapy.⁷⁵ Furthermore, exohedral decoration of MWCNTs with NH-aziridine groups *via* (2+1)-cycloaddition of *t*-Boc-nitrene, followed by thermal decomposition of the cyclization product, displayed catalytic activity in the Knoevenagel condensation and the oxygen activation/electrochemical reduction.⁷⁶ Further, MWCNTs amino-functionalized *via* (2+1)-cycloaddition of alkyl terminal nitrenes displayed a 12 times higher activity than the non-functionalized MWCNTs and 40% higher activity than the non-covalent MWCNT-enzyme hybrid. Critically, the stereoselectivity of MWCNT-NH₂-enzyme was found to be two times greater than in the hybrid with the non-covalently immobilized lipase.⁷⁷ Azido-dichlorotriazine was also employed as an *in-situ* precursor of the nitrene functionalizing SWCNTs. In a single-step synthesis, ring-opening and rehybridization possibly led to a hetero-bridged nanotube formation – as anticipated by highly strained nitrene adducts. Thus, even if the addend caused a slight corrugation, the electron lone pair of the bridging nitrogen atom could join the SWCNT π -conjugated system and increase the net electron density in the final structure.⁷⁸

The ‘onion effect’ (progressive wall-by-wall unsheathing of nanotubes) limits the number of protic functional groups anchorable to MWCNTs *via* oxidation. Nevertheless, pre-oxidized and pre-*N*-doped MWCNTs were modified *via* (2+1)-cycloaddition of the *in situ* generated nitrenes which yielded a 17.4% degree of functionalization of MWCNTs by hydrophilic salicylic acid moieties. The relaxivity (a measure of the capacity of contrast agents used in magnetic resonance spectroscopy to slow down the relaxation of protons of water molecules) has increased by about 30% because of the introduction of oxygen functional groups. After subcutaneous injection into a mouse, the resultant nanohybrids exhibited low cytotoxicity and excellent diffusion paving the way to modern biocompatible nanotube MRI contrast agents.⁷⁹

3.4 (3+2)-Cycloaddition

Cyclic nitrones employed to functionalize MWCNTs furnished highly dispersible functional materials.⁸⁰ Chemical and spectroscopic analysis thereof revealed side-wall defects as the MWCNT reactive sites. Indeed, nitron functionalization was found to preserve the majority of sp^2 -carbon hybridization in the CNT lattice and, thus, emerged as a potential alternative to the non-covalent functionalization.

SWCNT-NH₂ arose as reactive fillers covalently linkable to the epoxy matrix. As compared to the non-functionalized SWCNTs, SWCNT-NH₂ epoxy composites showed enhanced mechanical, electrical, and thermal characteristics.⁸¹ SWCNT-NH₂ was synthesized *via* a diazonium salt reaction from 4-aminobenzylamine. This approach was found to effectively improve the tensile and impact properties of the epoxy composites. An impact strength of 44% was recorded for the epoxy composite containing 0.1 wt.% of SWCNT-NH₂, which is a 90% improvement compared to the 'blank' sample.

Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) and poly(α -chloro- ϵ -caprolactone) (PaCl-CL) were polymerized *via* co-initiating reaction by MWCNT-OH.⁸² Conversion of the dangling chlorine atoms to the azide groups took place by the reaction with NaN₃ and the pendent azides facilitated the reaction with terminal alkynes during the Cu-catalyzed Huisgen (3+2)-cycloaddition. The polymer-grafted nanotubes displayed improved dispersibility in CHCl₃ compared to THF. The average polymer layer thickness was 8-10 nm and 3 nm for MWCNT-g-PCL and MWCNT grafted with poly(α -azo- ϵ -caprolactone), respectively. Similarly, adsorption of SWCNTs onto a glass carbon electrode *via* electrochemical grafting, followed by covalent bonding of ferrocene, led to 4-azidobenzenediazonium salt grafting *via* electrochemical reduction. Further, the copper-catalyzed reaction of surface-grafted azide groups with ethynyl-ferrocene enabled the formation of 1,2,3-

triazole units. By integrating high electrical conductivity, enhanced surface area of the nanotubes, and the adaptability of the Sharpless click reaction, this layer-by-layer fabrication produced stable electrodes.⁸³ Similar to the design of SWCNT-based gas sensing layers, the reaction between monoalkyne-substituted 3-phenyl coumarin and azide-modified SWCNTs was carried out. 3-Phenylcoumarin molecules served as the nanotube linkers. Importantly, hybrids based on covalently functionalized CNTs displayed 4 times higher sensor response to ammonia than hybrids based on non-covalently modified CNTs.⁸⁴

SWCNTs were functionalized *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition, under microwave (MW) heating, with a stable azomethine imine, i.e., 3-phenyl-phthalazinium-1-olate.⁸⁵ Solvent-free MW irradiation allowed also functionalization of SWCNTs with enantiopure carbonyl generated from epoxides of (*R*)-pulegone and (*R*)-carvone *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition. The degree of functionalization indicated the presence of one functional group per 55, 151, and 217 carbons atoms, respectively for *gem*-dicyano-, (*R*)-pulegone-, and (*R*)-carvone-modified CNTs. SEM imaging indicated negligible dielectric heating-induced damage to the carbon skeleton in the functionalized CNTs while their dispersibility in water was found substantially enhanced.⁸⁶

Tunable, from-water-to-organic-solvent, dispersibility of SWCNTs was stated as possible in a multi-functionalization study. Amidation of ionic liquid precursors on oxidized SWCNTs, followed by the treatment with *n*-butyl bromide, led to a subsequent addition of 11,11,12,12-tetracyano-9,10-anthra-paraquinonedimethane (TCAQ) *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition. An alternative route of TCAQ anchoring *via* esterification, followed by the Tour reaction, was employed to study the effect of the attached group position. The latter route was found to incorporate a lower number of functional units to SWCNTs, however, tunable polarity was achievable *via* both approaches.⁸⁷

Oxazolones are known 1,3-dipoles in the solid-solid (3+2)-cycloaddition reactions. A reaction of oxazolone (4-methyl-2-phenyloxazol-5(4*H*)-one) with MWCNTs was anticipated to graft Δ -1-pyrroline moieties onto the MWCNT surface. Oxazolone, with its oxazolium-5-oxide tautomer (münchnone), upon losing CO₂, yielded the corresponding ylide which attacked MWCNT. The degree of functionalization achieved in this study (4.8%) corresponded to one Δ -1-pyrroline unit per 206 carbon atoms.⁸⁸

Acid-cut hence biocompatible nanotubes reacted with 3-azidopropylamine *via* *N*-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-*N*'-ethyl carbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) leading to azide functionalized CNTs (N₃-CNTs). Because of the low dispersibility in both organic solvents and water, N₃-CNTs were further transformed into Boc-K3-CNT (*N*-*tert*-butoxy carbonyl protected oligolysine (K3)-CNT) composite. The resultant CNTs – owing to the grafting of oligo-lysine dendrons – displayed an enhanced water and organic solvent affinity compared to the acid-cut and azide functionalized CNTs.⁸⁹

Huisgen (3+2)-cycloaddition was also applied to modify SWCNTs by their conjugation with alkyne-modified protein toward immunoassay sensing. The resultant SWCNTs displayed enhanced water dispersibility and bioactivity for the model proteins: immunoglobulin (IgG) and horseradish peroxidase. Surface immobilization of IgG-functionalized SWCNTs on glassy carbon electrodes served as immunogens or for the detection of anti-immunoglobulin at the level of detection limit up to 30 pg mL⁻¹.⁹⁰ Likewise, core-shell Fe@Au NPs were click-coupled to MWCNTs *via* a two-step reverse micelle process. Using the thiol affinity toward Au, Fe@Au NPs were treated with 4-azidobutane-1-thiol to synthesize azide-modified NPs. Alkyne-functionalized MWCNTs were produced *via* solvent-free diazotization and coupling with *p*-aminophenyl propargyl ether. Cu(I)-catalyzed (3+2)-cycloaddition between azide-functionalized Fe@Au NPs

and alkyne-functionalized MWCNTs produced the target nanohybrids. According to superconducting quantum interference device (SQUID) study, the Fe@Au/MWCNTs nanohybrids displayed ferromagnetic activity at ambient temperature with very small coercivity or remanence. The magnetic nanohybrids were found to be highly magnetically sensitive in a colloidal suspension.⁹¹

Palladium NPs of an enhanced electrocatalytic activity were grafted onto ionic liquid- (IL) functionalized CNTs.⁹² The resultant Pd@IL(Cl)-CNT catalyst displayed an improved tolerance to poisoning, electrocatalytic activity, and stability compared to Pd NPs immobilized onto CNTs, owing to the effect of IL intrusion. Additionally, pyrrolidine-CNTs were obtained upon treatment of nanotubes with the azomethine ylide toward the enhanced physicochemical compatibility with amide groups of polyamide-6 (PA6), and indeed the so-functionalized CNTs improved the CNT/PA6 interface.⁹³ In a similar study, functionalized CNTs were more readily and more efficiently dispersible in poly(lactic acid) (PLA).⁹⁴

Interestingly, solid-state functionalization of CNTs *via* a similar reaction scheme was also successful upon employing sarcosine and 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde as 1,3-dipole precursors.⁹⁵ The resultant functionalized CNTs displayed an enhanced dispersibility in water and alcohols paving the way to conductive inks. This functionalization methodology allowed us to obtain nanoCu and nanoAg-CNT hybrids of an improved to-nanotube adhesion.⁹⁶

Michael-type addition of methyl acrylate to amino-linker-CNTs (obtained from azomethine ylide) enabled aminolysis of ester groups toward nanotubes with dendritic arms; the arms bearing a substantial number of amino groups acted as diverse anchors.⁹⁷ The ability of the amino groups to anchor redox-active transition metal NPs facilitated the design of water splitting electrode. Also,

C₆₀ and MWCNTs equipped with Ru(III)-chelating tridentate ligand, i.e., terpyridyl-pyrrolidine, were synthesized *via* (3+2)-dipolar cycloaddition.⁹⁸

Purine/pyrimidine and purine/purine derivatives were employed for the double functionalization of SWCNTs *via* amidation of carboxylic groups or (3+2)-cycloaddition enabling formation of DNA sorting sensors *via* Watson-crick base pairing.⁹⁹ Similarly, double-functionalized MWCNTs served as probes of an aspect-ratio-governed affinity to tissues higher found for 10-nm-thin MWCNTs.¹⁰⁰

Amidation was also employed to functionalize MWCNT-COOH with 2,2':6'2''-terpyridine-chelated ruthenium(II) yielding deteriorated MWCNT characteristics¹⁰¹ while porphyrin-functionalized MWCNTs, i.e., with 5-[4-(2(4-formylphenoxy)ethoxy)phenyl]-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin (TPP) and 5-[4-(4-formylphenyl)ethynyl phenyl]-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrinato zinc(II) (ZnTPP), obtained *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition of azomethine ylides, displayed retention of the inherent electronic and mechanical properties.¹⁰² Also, azomethine ylide bearing a beta-cyclodextrin (β -CD) and 1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane-*N,N',N'',N'''*-tetraacetic acid monoamide (DOTAMA) moiety were used for the (preferential tip) multi-functionalization of SWCNTs.¹⁰³

MW-assisted (3+2)-cycloaddition of SWCNTs was achieved also by *in situ* reacting Kröhnke salts, i.e., sodium *N*-(4-methylbenzenesulfonate)pyridinium bromide and *N*-(4-nitrobenzyl)pyridinium bromide, with triethylamine.¹⁰⁴ A substantial effect of the electron-withdrawing groups was observed on the reactivity of pyridinium ylides as (-SO₃⁻Na⁺) suppressed pyridinium ylide reactivity because of the large HOMO-LUMO gap. The reduction of groups linked to the indolizine ring aided the generation of luminous SWCNTs.

Oxidation of MWCNTs using piranha solution (leading to a partial thickening via CNT ‘subzipping’ and cutting), followed by (3+2)-cycloaddition with 3,4-dihydroxy benzaldehyde and *N*-methyl glycine, led to the azomethine ylide functionalized MWCNTs, which further underwent silanization. This three-step functionalization induced substantial hydrophobicity in MWCNTs which facilitated the production of differently (non-)wetable composites.¹⁰⁵

Under MW-irradiation, ester-functionalized SWCNTs underwent a (3+2)-cycloaddition reaction with nitrile imine, yielding a double-ester-terminated SWCNT cycloadduct.¹⁰⁶ In an attempt to develop thiol-terminated SWCNT templates, the ester terminals were further altered with 4-aminothiophenol. This protocol generated a hybrid nanomaterial with reactive ‘hotspots’ and improved water stability which also displayed a greater extent of covalent bonding to gold ‘nano-popcorn’. As anticipated, such a nanohybrid displayed an impressive surface-enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) activity as well as served as an excellent *E. coli* detector.

Pyridinium-ylide-functionalized SWCNTs reacted with dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition yielding blue-light-emitting indolizine-SWCNTs upon excitement at 330 nm. 4-Nitrophenol derivatives suppressed fluorescence in such modified SWCNTs – both in solution and in a solid state – likely due to strong *H*-bonding between the host and guest molecules.¹⁰⁷

Azide-functionalized MWCNTs bearing carboxylic moieties enhanced the stability of aqueous dispersion enabling efficient inkjet printing.¹⁰⁸ Contrarily, SWCNTs functionalized *via* azide-alkyne reaction were employed to synthesize superhydrophobic polymer applicable in the leather industry.¹⁰⁹

Aldehyde conversion to aldoximes, followed by base-induced chlorination, led to RC^+NO^- 1,3-dipoles generating isoxazole-functionalized CNTs in which a degree of functionalization was directly proportional to a number of the crystallographic defects in the pristine nanotubes.¹¹⁰

3.5 (4+2)-Cycloaddition

Cyclopentadienyl end-capped poly(methyl methacrylate) was reacted with SWCNTs *via* catalyst-free (4+2)-cycloaddition, enabling a quantitative access to cyclopentadienyl-capped macromolecules.¹¹¹ A polymer chain density of 0.027 nm⁻² was attained when SWCNTs were functionalized *via* a single-step Diels-Alder reaction with end-capped polystyrene at ca. 230 °C (Figure 5).¹¹²

Figure 5 (a) Functionalization of SWCNTs with cyclopentadiene-capped poly(methyl methacrylate). Reproduced from the study by Zydziak *et al.*¹¹¹ with permission. Copyright 2021, The Authors, Published by MDPI. (b) Synthetic strategy for the synthesis and surface functionalization of end-capped PS-(diphenylene cyclobutene). Reproduced from the study by Stathouraki *et al.*¹¹² with permission. Copyright 2021, The Authors, Published by MDPI.

Diels-Alder cycloaddition of 1,3-butadiene (produced *in situ* from sulfolene) to CNTs was performed at elevated temperature.¹¹³ Importantly, the cyclohexene ring grafted on a nanotube wall quickly oxidized or reacted with the second butadiene unit (in the presence of ambient oxygen). The oxidation persisted until the total consumption of alkene groups formed the

anhydride moieties in a highly exothermic process stabilizing the product whereas, under N₂, the conjugated carbon surface did not preserve the cyclohexene unit.

Barothermal Diels-Alder reaction of MWCNTs with dienophiles including *p*-benzoquinone, maleimide, and fumaronitrile, led to the novel functional materials.¹¹⁴ Thermal studies revealed that (4+2)-cycloaddition involved up to 5% of the carbon atoms.

The nature of CNTs is a deciding factor in the topology of cycloadditions. As theoretical calculations have shown, functionalization of SWCNTs with multiple arynes under MW-irradiation unveiled the thermal stability of mostly zigzag SWCNT (4+2)-cycloadducts.¹¹⁵

3.6 PEGylation

PEGylation is the most widely implemented strategy to enhance the biocompatibility and stability of the aqueous CNT dispersions. However, PEGylation has a few limitations which lead to an overall low cellular uptake, inefficient biodegradation, and cost-ineffectiveness of the CNT hybrids. As a promising alternative strategy toward functionalization of MWCNTs, protein succinylated β -lactoglobulin (Sblg) was used (**Figure 6**).¹¹⁶

Figure 6 (a) Synthesis of Sblg-f-MWCNTs; (b) Dispersion stability analysis in deionized water: just dispersed (*upper panel*), after 15 days (*middle panel*), and after 30 days (*below panel*) for samples: (i) P-MWCNTs, (ii) ox-MWCNT, (iii) PEGylated dispersion, and (iv) Sblg-f-MWCNTs. Reproduced from the study by Jain *et al.*¹¹⁶ with permission. Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society.

Sblg-functionalized MWCNTs were found less cost-demanding and to have a 5-6-fold higher IC_{50} value than the pristine MWCNTs in the *in vitro* studies, while the stability of both PEG-f-MWCNT and Sblg-f-MWCNT aqueous dispersions was found to be almost similar, i.e., one month.

4 Carbon nanofibers

A non-continuous, 1D carbon nanoallotrope with a cylindrical or conical shape – of different configurations of stacked and bent graphene sheets – is called CNF. Prior to the advent of CNTs, CNFs had already been thoroughly investigated. They are typically defined as sp^2 -based linear filaments with diameters between 50 and 200 nm and an aspect ratio of >100 . There are five types

of CNFs categorized according to their internal structure, i.e., platelet, herringbone/fishbone, ribbon/tubular, stacked-cup/cone-stacked, and cone-helix CNFs (**Figure 7**).

Figure 7 Arrangement of graphene sheets in different types of CNF: a)- fishbone CNF, b)- platelet CNF, c)- stacked-cup CNF, d)- ribbon CNF, and e)- tubular CNF.

The perpendicular orientation of the graphene layers with respect to the fiber axis gives rise to platelet CNFs. In turn, CNFs based on graphene sheets tilted toward the fiber axis are called herringbone or fishbone CNFs. Ribbon or tubular CNFs originate from the parallel orientation of stacked graphene nanosheets to the fiber axis. CNFs with a truncated cone arrangement and a hollow core are called stacked-cup or cone-stacked CNFs. Continuous helix-spiral frameworks and hollow cores are associated with cone-helix CNFs. The hollow cavity of CNTs distinguishes them from CNFs. For the purpose of distinguishing CNTs and CNF from cones and tilted graphene sheets, an angle (α) is specified. It accounts for where the graphene sheet is located in relation to the sidewall of CNF. CNFs of tilted graphene sheets are characterized by $\alpha > 0$. CNFs are generally among the moderately explored classes of carbon nanoallotropes.

4.1 (2+1)-Cycloaddition

CNFs of 10-40 nm length reacted with 4-(azidomethyl)benzoic acid (4-AMBA) *via* (2+1)-nitrene cycloaddition.¹¹⁷ Conventionally, (2+1)-cycloaddition reactions are carried out by thermal heating

which results in rather moderate yields at the prolonged reaction times. This reaction was carried out by the employment of MWs which facilitated the from-azido-to-nitrene (a biradical nitrene form) conversion. The overall decrease in I_D/I_G ratio paved the way for the hypothesis that aziridine ring formation occurred preferentially at the structural CNF imperfections.

4.2 (3+2)-Cycloaddition

CNF surface typically needs a substantial chemical modification to craft composite materials of improved properties. Cyclic amine groups were introduced on the CNF surface *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition of azomethine ylides.¹¹⁸ These groups facilitated an amide link formation with the anhydride groups grafted on polypropylene enhancing the nanofiber/polymer interface. Generally, amino-azomethine-functionalized CNFs would enable grafting complex molecules to the CNF surface in a variety of composites.¹¹⁷

5 Graphene, graphenoids and (r-)GO – 2D nanocarbons

Graphene is among the most widely explored carbon nanoallotropes. It is a building block of graphite, which is one of the most abundant carbon materials. Covalent σ -bonds link each carbon atom in a graphene sheet to three adjacent carbon atoms, forming a robust honeycomb lattice.¹¹⁹ The aromatic properties of graphene originate from the overlap of the unhybridized *p*-orbitals, perpendicularly oriented to the planar graphene sheet. The number of graphene monolayers and the optical transmittance of graphene (which is 97.5% for monolayers) are inversely proportional.¹²⁰ Concerning the synthesis of graphene, the crystallographic quality, morphology, and yield *per carbon* (%) are directly related to the synthesis approach opted for. Generally, defect sites contribute to the poor electrical and mechanical properties of graphene materials.⁴⁶

Additionally, the size of graphene nanoplatelets is often constrained, while numerous synthetic approaches produce multilayered graphene nanosheets. The Raman spectra of graphene nanoplatelets contain distinct G-bands at 1580 cm^{-1} , D-bands at 1350 cm^{-1} , and a 2D-band at 2700 cm^{-1} , just like other 2D carbon nanoallotropes.¹²¹

The aromatic rings directly linked to the edges and defect sites of sp^3 -carbon atoms activate the D-band because of their A_{1g} vibrations.¹²² The proportion of sp^3 -carbon atoms in the graphitic nanostructure, which typically represents the most abundant defect sites, apart from edge atoms, including those in the gaps, is indicated by the $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio.¹²³ Therefore, Raman spectroscopy is an effective method for evaluating the quality of graphene samples due its unique spectroscopic characteristics. For instance, high-quality graphene flakes generated by liquid exfoliation of graphite show no or a D-band of a very weak intensity.

In comparison to the liquid-exfoliated graphene, graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) formed by GO reduction often have more defects and oxygen functionalities. Stacked from-two-to-ten graphene monolayers are called multilayer graphitic nanosheets which have properties near-like graphene as well as an enhanced dispersibility in organic solvents. Multilayered graphene nanosheet (MGNs) structure is demonstrated by both G- (1600 cm^{-1}) and D- (1385 cm^{-1}) bands.¹²⁴ In turn, a clear IR-band at 1725 cm^{-1} is attributed to the carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) groups, while a broad band between 1500 and 900 cm^{-1} is due to the O-H and C-O deformation and stretching vibrations, respectively. The process utilized to create the MGNs is responsible for the development of those functional groups. Also, graphene nanoribbons (GNRs), generated from the unzipping of CNTs, have received recently a significant attention. A common description of GNRs is that they are one-dimensional, sp^2 -hybridized carbon strips with defined edges and non-3-coordinated carbon

atoms. Based on the edge termination, GNRs can be classified as an armchair and zigzag nanoribbons (**Figure 8**).¹²⁵

Figure 8 Schemes of the structures of: a)- zigzag GNRs, b)- armchair GNRs.

The number of dimer C-C lines and zigzag chains across the nanoribbons is an indicative of the width of the armchair and zigzag carbon nanoribbons, respectively. The unsaturated carbon-carbon bonds at the edges make the edge reconstruction possible. The stable edge reconstruction of armchair GNRs is attributed to strong dangling bonds while for zigzag GNRs an enhanced temperature is required for the edge reconstruction.¹²⁶ Hydrogen saturation is frequently used for edge structure stabilization. Additional edge profiles, incorporating pentagonal and heptagonal carbon rings, have been reported, although, such edge reconstructions are exceptionally rare. Hybrid GNRs are those that often combine different edges; those structures are most typically found with heterojunctions of the armchair and zigzag patterns. GNRs can display bi-layered or few-layered patterns, like graphene. GNRs generated from MWCNTs, owing to the larger edge-to-surface ratios and an enhanced number of defect sites, display a strong D-band in the Raman spectrum. The ‘all-scale’ structures, frequently synthesis-driven, of a variety of graphene and

graphenoid materials used for functionalization and documented in this review are summarized in

Table 2.

Table 2 Summary of the graphene/graphenoids employed for the covalent functionalization

Type	Structure	Properties	Feedstock	(Pre-)Synthesis
Graphene	Covalent σ -bonds link each carbon atom in a graphene sheet to three adjacent carbon atoms, forming a robust honeycomb lattice. Pristine graphene does not have any functional groups attached	High electrical conductivity, exceptional mechanical strength, and large surface area.	Low-molecular-weight precursors, or graphite.	Chemical vapor deposition (CVD), physical or chemical exfoliation of graphite
Graphene oxide (GO)	Graphene with oxygen-containing functional groups attached, such as hydroxyl (-OH), epoxy (>O), or carboxyl (-COOH) groups	Improved dispersibility in polar media, lower electrical conductivity as compared to graphene	Graphite	Hummers method and modified Hummers methods
Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs)	Nano-sized platelets of graphene. Treatment processes may introduce or modify functional groups on the edges or surfaces of the nanoplatelets	Thin, plate-like morphology, high surface area, reduced electrical conductivity as compared to graphene	Graphite	Liquid phase exfoliation
Reduced graphene oxide (rGO)	GO with a fewer oxygen-functional groups. Reduction restores the sp^2 -carbon framework, enhancing properties such as electrical conductivity or mechanical strength	Restored electrical conductivity, reduced defects compared to GO, lower conductivity than pristine graphene	Graphene oxide (GO)	Electrochemical and chemical reduction of GO
Nanographene	Nano-sized sheets of graphene	Nanoscale dimensions, electrical and thermal properties comparable to that of graphene	Carbon precursors (e.g., hydrocarbons, CNTs, etc.)	Bottom-up synthesis
Few-layer-graphene (FLG)	Stacked layers of hexagonally arranged carbon atoms ranging from two to multiple layers. Functional groups such as hydroxyl, epoxy, or carboxyl may be present on the edges or surfaces of the layers in case of few layer GO or functionalized few-layer graphene (FLG)	Few-layer structure, high aspect ratio, properties approaching those of graphene	Graphite	Physical or chemical exfoliation

5.1 Electrophilic and nucleophilic addition

Synthesis of water-added graphite intercalation compounds (GICs) supports the preparation of few-layer graphene without oxidation. However, the technique lacks in imparting a large surface area to the final product. Thus, with an aim to acquire a large area of few-layer graphene, an aldehyde addition to GICs was investigated.¹²⁷ Electron withdrawing groups, preferentially in long alkyl chains of aldehydes, facilitated electrophilic addition to graphene.

In an attempt to broaden the scope of graphene applications in organic photo-electronics and polymer composites, the dispersibility of GO in a non-polar organic solvent, i.e., *ortho*-dichlorobenzene (ODCB) was investigated. The nucleophilic addition of *n*-butyllithium (*n*-BuLi) to GO sheets, followed by the coupling and etherification of the intermediates (Bu-GO)ⁿ⁻Liⁿ⁺ and 2-ethylhexyl bromide, resulted in the functionalized GO (**Figure 9**).

Figure 9 Synthesis of alkyl-functionalized GO proceeds *via* GO reaction with *n*-BuLi and 2-ethylhexyl bromide. Reproduced from the study by Huang *et al.*¹²⁸ with permission. Copyright 2012 Wiley-VCH GmbH & Co.

The study revealed a covalent link of *n*-Bu and 2-ethylhexyl to the GO sheets, and the production of numerous sp^3 -carbon atoms accompanied by the preserved structural integrity and an enhanced dispersibility of f-GO in ODCB to 0.4 mg mL^{-1} . Notably, annealing of f-GO in ODCB led to a conductive film as a potential candidate for the electrode materials.¹²⁸ Studies related to the functionalization of 2D nanocarbons by nucleophilic and electrophilic addition reactions are summarized in **Table 3**.

Table 3 Functionalization of 2D-nanocarbons *via* nucleophilic and electrophilic addition

References	Reactant	<i>In situ</i> produced reagent	Mechanism	Degree of functionalization	Application
Jaiswal <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹²⁹	GO-acyl chloride fulleranol [(Fol) ⁿ⁻ anion]	---	Nucleophilic addition-elimination		Hybrid electrode material
Guo <i>et al.</i> 2015 ¹³⁰	GO 4,6-Diaminoresorcinol dihydrochloride (DAR×2HCl), a monomer of PBO	---	Nucleophilic addition and E1-dehydration		rGO sheets
Arzani <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹³¹	Tetrahydrofurfuryl-GNP, PEG	---	Electrophilic addition	---	Nanofluid
Amiri <i>et al.</i> 2015 ¹³²	GNP PEG, 4-phenylazophenol (Azo)	---	Electrophilic addition	---	Engine coolant
Amiri <i>et al.</i> 2015 ¹³³	GNP ethylene glycol	----	Electrophilic addition	---	Improved dispersibility and colloidal stability
Yu <i>et al.</i> 2013 ¹³⁴	GO, sodium 4-aminoazobenzene-4-sulfonate (SAS), aryl diazonium salt (ADS)	---	SAS reacts with graphene <i>via</i> nucleophilic while ADS <i>via</i> electrophilic addition	---	Improved electrical properties
Gowthaman <i>et al.</i> 2017 ¹³⁵	GO, caffeinic acid	---	Reduction	---	Reduced cytotoxicity
Hu <i>et al.</i> 2014 ¹³⁶	GO, Polydopamine, fullerene	---	Michael-type (nucleophilic) addition	---	Protective agent against NO-induced cytotoxicity
Hu <i>et al.</i> 2015 ¹³⁷	GO, folic acid, poly(ethylene glycol)	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Improved phototoxicity
Yan <i>et al.</i> 2015 ¹³⁸	Vinyltriethoxysilane-grafted GO, Hyperbranched polysiloxane monomers	---	Hydrosilylation	---	Improved tribological performance
Akhtar <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹³⁹	Few-layer-graphene, <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine (OPD)	---	Amidation/ nucleophilic addition	---	Improved thermal conductivity and stability

Dhahri <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹⁴⁰	Covalent grafting of GO with ethylenediamine followed by the reaction with chlorocellulose and deposition of Au NPs	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Improved electrical conductivity
Upadhyay <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹⁴¹	GO, polyethylene	---	Nucleophilic addition-elimination	---	Biocomposites
Chhetri <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁴²	GO, 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (TZ) and potassium hydroxide (KOH)	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Improved fracture toughness and thermal stability
Xu <i>et al.</i> 2017 ¹⁴³	rGO and TPE/carbazole/phenyl group containing polymers	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Optical limiting properties
Yang <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁴⁴	GO, thiourea	---	Dehydration condensation and nucleophilic addition	---	Membranes for separation of small molecules
Hu <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁴⁵	Oxo-G, FeCl ₂ , H ₂ O ₂	---	Electrophilic addition and oxidation responsible for etching	---	Optical Properties
Jin <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁴⁶	GO, NH ₃	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Corrosion inhibition
Yang <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁴⁷	For rGO-PDA, GO and dopamine hydrochloride used toward further modification with an electrophilic conjugated system	---	Michael addition/Schiff-base reaction	---	Electrochemical chiral interface
Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁴⁸	GO, tetrabutylammonium hydroxide and 1-aza-18-crown-6 ether	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Electrochemical sensor for potassium ion
Khan <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁴⁹	GO, propylamine, benzoquinone	---	Ring opening of epoxide/nucleophilic addition	---	Electrode material
Samanta <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁵⁰	GO and branched polyethylenimine	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Tribological Properties
Yan <i>et al.</i> 2015 ¹⁵¹	Reaction of rGO and <i>n</i> -BuLi, followed by a subsequent coupling of intermediates (<i>n</i> -Bu-rGO) _{<i>n</i>} -Li ⁿ⁺ with an alkyl halide	---	Nucleophilic addition	1 functional group per 20-60 carbon atoms	Controllable dispersibility in polar and non-polar solvents
Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁵²	GO, <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine (PDA), and benzidine (DAB)	---	Nucleophilic addition	---	Capacitive deionization electrode

Yu <i>et al.</i> 2022 ¹⁵³			Nucleophilic addition and amide reaction	---	Capacitive deionization electrode
Xu <i>et al.</i> 2012 ¹⁵⁴	GO, poly(9,9'-dihexylfluorene carbazole)	Nitrogen-centered anion	Nucleophilic addition-elimination		Optical limiting properties

Graphene-polydopamine-C₆₀ nanohybrid was investigated in cell and cell-free conditions for nitric oxide (NO) induced cytotoxicity inhibition.¹³⁶ Surface modification and reduction of GO *via* polydopamine (PDA) chemistry followed by nucleophilic addition led to a nanohybrid rGO-PDA-C₆₀. The enhanced cellular uptake of rGO-PDA-C₆₀ was attributed to suppressed C₆₀ aggregation because of the firm C₆₀ fixation on graphene *via* the nucleophilic addition. A direct NO scavenging was observed and presented the NO-mediated cell injury prevention ability of nanocarbons.

Covalent grafting of PEG and folic acid on GO followed by nucleophilic addition of C₆₀ led to FA-GO-PEG/C₆₀ nanohybrid.¹³⁷ Nucleophilic addition occurred across the C=C skeleton of GO and the amino groups of FA-GO-PEG. This nanohybrid was explored for the first time toward the tumor targeting and was found to enhance the therapeutic efficiency by synergizing the effects of photodynamic and photothermal therapy. Additionally, the colloidal stability of graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) in aqueous media was improved by their functionalization with tetrahydrofurfuryl-modified PEG *via* electrophilic addition. The resultant heat transfer nanofluid (a coolant) had an improved convective heat transfer coefficient.¹³¹ Ethylene glycol-treated GNPs emerged as excellent engine coolants,¹³³ while GNPs – functionalized with PEG and 4-phenylazophenol *via* the microwave-facilitated electrophilic addition – led to their improved dispersibility in different media as compared to the pristine GNPs.¹³²

Nucleophilic addition was employed to synthesize fullerene-functionalized GO (FGO) and reduced-FGO nanohybrids. Capacitance, energy density, and the power density of nanohybrids was found to be higher than of fullerene or GO alone. Moreover, rFGO found to have a higher

capacitance (368 F g^{-1} after 1000 cycles), energy density ($51.11 \text{ W h kg}^{-1}$ in $1 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$), and power density (5018 W kg^{-1} in $1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$) than FGO, which can be attributed to precipitation of attached $-\text{COOH}$ groups during the network formation.¹²⁹

Hyperbranched polysilane (HBPSi) grafted onto rGO was incorporated into bismaleimide (BMI) resin to obtain the composites of enhanced thermal and mechanical properties (**Figure 10**).¹⁵⁵ BMI resin with 0.6 wt.% of HBPSi-rGO content was found to have an improved impact and flexural strengths, compared to the neat BMI resin, of 62.6% and 20.2%, respectively. Nucleophilic addition imparted the enhanced interfacial bonding between BMI and HBPSi-rGO and was found to play a role in this phenomenon by preventing the composite fracture. The overall enhanced thermal decomposition resistance was also attributed to the improved covalent crosslinking.

Figure 10 The synthetic route to HBPSi-rGO. Reproduced from the study by Yan *et al.*¹⁵⁵ with permission. Copyright 2015 The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Treatment of graphene with an $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4\text{:HNO}_3$ mixture of the 2:6 molar ratio, followed by simple reflux of a ‘double *N*-precursor’, i.e., *o*-phenylenediamine (OPD), formed the oxygen

groups on the graphene surface.¹³⁹ The so-introduced amine groups facilitated further nitrogen doping into graphene layers *via* amidation and nucleophilic addition. The OPD-functionalized graphene was homogeneously dispersed in the epoxy matrix and resulted in the functionalized graphene epoxy composite of in-plane thermal conductivity 13 folds and through-plane 4.8 folds higher than the neat epoxy resin. The enhanced thermal conductivity was attributed to the phonon conduction pathways generated *via* mixing the filler with FG-epoxy (functionalized graphene-filled epoxy). Intercalation of GO with melamine *via* sonication led to nitrogen-doped GO (N-GO). Amine groups of N-GO facilitated the attachment on glassy carbon electrode (GCE) *via* the Michael-type addition. Electrochemical reduction of oxygen functional groups from the surface of N-GO/GCE facilitated electrodeposition of Cu NPs. The resultant glucose monitor displayed a two-fold higher glucose oxidation current than the sensors based on N-GO and Cu NPs.¹³⁵

Covalent grafting of ethylenediamine onto the GO sheets *via* nucleophilic addition, followed by reduction with hydrazine and reaction with chloro-cellulose, also led to the functionalized GO.¹⁴⁰ Further, the reduction of Au³⁺ deposited Au NPs on the functionalized GO sheets containing 45 wt.% of grafted cellulose and 15 wt.% of Au NPs. The functionalized material displayed electroconductivity of $4.8 \times 10^{-2} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$, hence, its applications as biosensors and biocatalysts were indicated as the most promising ones.

Polyethylene (PE) was tethered to GO sheets by a nucleophilic addition-elimination reaction to control the dispersibility of GO and to enhance interfacial adhesion.¹⁴¹ High-density polyethylene (HDPE) composite reinforced with 3 wt.% PE-grafted GO displayed a yield strength of 20 MPa and an elastic modulus of 600 MPa, which corresponded to 30% and 40% higher than for its unmodified counterpart, respectively. The reinforced HDPE was indicated as a potential candidate for orthopedic applications. Similarly, rGO was compatibilized with epoxy matrices

using 3-amino-1,2,4-triazole (TZ) (KOH served as a catalyst), but the interactions between the epoxy and rGO-TZ remained non-covalent.¹⁴² The reaction between rGO and TZ was proceeding *via* nucleophilic addition-elimination (NH₂ vs. COOH) and addition (NH₂ vs. C=C). Fracture toughness, tensile strength, and Young's modulus of the composite, in respect to epoxy matrix, were enhanced by 111%, 30.5%, and 35%, respectively.

Three conjugated polymers, each with different monomers, including tetraphenylethylene (TPE), carbazole, and phenyl groups, were used for the functionalization of rGO.¹⁴³ Sodium hydride was employed for the deprotonation of NH moieties in the monomer. Despite having the same reactive sites, each polymer displayed a difference in reactivities attributed to the different monomers used. π - π Interactions and the 'polymer wrapping effect between rGO and polymers diversified the dispersion stability and optical limiting performances of composites. In another study, dispersibility of hydrophobic polymer PCF (poly (9,9'-dihexylfluorene carbazole)) in water was improved by wrapping it with rGO. Sodium hydride functioned as reducing agent to partially reduce GO and as a deprotonating agent to convert nitrogen atoms of PCF into nitrogen-centered anions, which led to a subsequent nucleophilic addition to GO. Improved dispersibility of rGO-PCF was attributed to the splitting into 200-nm-wide platelets and excellent optical limiting properties as compared to the larger sizes of rGO in the insoluble part.¹⁵⁴

2D-stacked GO membranes are widely explored for gases, ions, and liquids separation owing to their accommodating molecular sieving abilities. However, lacking interlamellar interactions leads to the substandard mechanical strength of the membranes hindering practical applications. Inherent, large-sized channels of stacked GO membranes impart low small molecule selectivity. To address the said issues, thiourea (TU) grafted GO membranes were developed on porous ceramics *via* hydrothermal self-assembly.¹⁴⁴ Dehydration condensation reaction between

NH₂ or SH and COOH groups as well as nucleophilic addition of -NH₂ to GO epoxy enabled membranes of narrow, well-defined channels. The membranes successfully held back large molecules upon pervaporation, such as C₂-C₄ alcohols mixed with 10 wt.% of water. As for desalination, TU-GOF membranes displayed a 99.8% rejection rate for all salts when tested for various saline solutions (0.01 mol L⁻¹) (**Figure 11**).

Figure 11 a) TU-GOF membrane permeance of gases ($\Delta P=0.2$ bar, 25 °C); b) gas separation performance of TU-GOF membrane in the background of other membranes (50 °C, $\Delta P=1.0$ bar); c) pervaporative separation performance of TU-GOF for H₂O-alcohol system and, d) stability of TU-GOF membrane for dehydration of EtOH (50 °C, 10% H₂O feed). Reproduced from the study by Yang *et al.*¹⁵⁶ with permission. Copyright 2018 Wiley-VCH GmbH & Co.

Also, nucleophilic addition of amine of TU/*m*-phenylenediamine (MPD) to GO epoxy groups paved a way to robust nanochannels enabling salt rejection by 95.6% for NaCl while only

moderately sacrificing the water permeability.¹⁵⁷ Concerning design of materials dedicated for the manufacturing of membranes, porosity of graphene materials was achieved by wet-chemistry oxidation etching.¹⁴⁵

GO-NH₂ (0.3 wt.)/epoxy composite served as a coating on Mg alloy proving its superior corrosion protection against 3.5 wt.% NaCl solutions.¹⁴⁶ rGO-PDA-L-Lys electroactive material, synthesized *via* a sequence of free-radical anchoring of PDA to rGO and the concomitant Michael addition and Cu²⁺ coordination, enabled discrimination of tryptophan enantiomers electrochemically.¹⁴⁷ Another ion-recognizing material, here dedicated to K⁺-sensing by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) of glass carbon electrode (GCE),¹⁴⁸ was formed by GO functionalization *via* nucleophilic addition of 1-aza-18-crown-6 (**Figure 12**).

Figure 12 EIS analysis of Crown-GO/GCE, GO/GCE, and GCE in 1.5 mM MB solution under 10mV amplitude, and frequency range of 1000000 Hz to 0.1 Hz. Reproduced from the study by Zhang *et al.*¹⁴⁸ with permission. Copyright 2019 IOP Publishing Ltd.

K⁺ concentration was found as inversely proportional to the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of the ultrasensitive crown-GO electrode with a 10^{-15} M detection limit.

Dual-functional GO-based materials, dedicated to fuel cell membranes of high proton conductivity and supercapacitors, were synthesized *via* the epoxy-ring opening induced by propylamines, followed by the nucleophilic addition of hydroxyl groups to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds, i.e., 2-aminonaphthoquinone and benzoquinone.¹⁴⁹ A nucleophilic addition reaction between polyethylenimine (PEI) and GO, followed by layer-by-layer assembly with anionic polyelectrolyte poly(acrylic acid sodium salt) (PAA) and sodium poly(4-styrenesulfonate) (PSS), facilitated the polymer brush fabrication. The resultant GO-PEI-PAA/GO-PEI-PSS reduced the coefficient of friction (COF) by 85% at 0.9 MPa compared with paraffin oil.¹⁵⁰ SAS (4-aminoazobenzene-4'-sulfonate) and its aryl diazonium salt (ADS) functionalized GO toward improved dispersibilities of 1.4 and 2.9 mg mL⁻¹ in water, respectively. Specific capacitance of 210 F g⁻¹ for ADS and 170 F g⁻¹ for the SAS functionalized GO was observed. Such a high capacitance and electrical conductivity of ADS-functionalized GO was attributed to the reduction of GO to graphene.¹³⁴

rGO was functionalized *via* a simple reaction sequence that employed nucleophilic addition of *n*-butyllithium to facilitate the succeeding intermediate (n-Bu-rGO)ⁿ-Liⁿ⁺ coupling with alkyl halides.¹⁵⁸ The resultant functionalized r-GO displayed enhanced and reversible dispersibility in both polar and non-polar solvents.

Nucleophilic addition, amidation, and electrostatic self-assembly were employed simultaneously for the synthesis of *p*-phenylenediamine or benzidine-functionalized rGO toward the enhanced conductivity and specific surface area to pore volume ratio;¹⁵² the high electrosorption capacities observed at 1.4 eV were determined as 7.88 mg g⁻¹ for Na⁺, 8.02 mg g⁻¹ for Mg²⁺, and 13.55 mg g⁻¹ for Ca²⁺. GO modified with protonated carbon nitride *via* a similar approach displayed electrosorption capacity of 8.36 mg g⁻¹ for Na⁺ at 1.2 V with the regeneration

efficiency as high as 100%.¹⁵³ In another study, 4,6-diaminoresocinol dihydrochloride – used as a monomer of PBO (poly(*p*-phenylenebenzobisoxazole)) – crystallized on a surface of rGO *via* nucleophilic addition and E1 dehydration, which led to rGO/PBO composite fibers. CNFs of high thermal stability and improved mechanical properties were obtained, i.e., tensile strength of 3.50 GPa and Young's modulus of 130 GPa.¹³⁰

5.2 Radical addition

Diradical generation from asymmetric enediyne moieties *via* Bergman cyclization, followed by polymer grafting (**Figure 13**), resulted in the exfoliated graphene material of high electroconductivity which was diminished after polymer grafting.¹⁵⁹

Figure 13 Functionalization of graphene with enediyne molecules. Reproduced from the study by Ma *et al.*¹⁵⁹ with permission. Copyright 2012 Wiley-VCH GmbH.

Diradicals limited the net number of defects in the graphene network to improve conductivity and broadened the possibilities to attach multiple functionalities to graphene/polymer composites. The

studies related to the functionalization of 2D-nanocarbons by radical addition are summarized in

Table 4.

Table 4 Functionalization of 2D-nanocarbons *via* radical addition.

Ref.	Reactant	<i>In situ</i> produced reagent	Mechanism	Degree of functionalization	Application
Ma <i>et al.</i> 2012 ¹⁵⁹	GO, enediyne molecules	---	Diradical addition and propagation	---	Dispersibility in organic solvents, electrical conductivity
Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2013 ¹⁶⁰	Graphene and 2,2-azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBN)	Azo	Free radical Addition	1 isobutyronitrile group per 50 carbon atoms	Improved dispersibility
Li <i>et al.</i> 2013 ¹⁶¹	GO and 3- [2-(2-aminoethylamino) ethylamino]propyl-trimethoxysilane (AEPTMS) to synthesize amine functionalized GO followed by radical addition	---	Silylation reaction and radical addition	---	Catalyst for acetalization–nitroaldol reaction
Guimont <i>et al.</i> 2014 ¹⁶²	GO, anhydrous 1,4-dioxane, and pentadecane further grafted with PE	---	Radical addition	---	Conductive composites
Peng <i>et al.</i> 2014 ¹⁶³	GO, modification reagents	---	Atom transfer radical polymerization (ATRP)	---	Dispersibility, stability
Cao <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁶⁴	GO-OH fabricated <i>via</i> diazonium addition reaction followed by reaction with 2-bromopropionyl bromide to form GO-Br; grafting by poly(hexadecyl acrylate)	---	Surface-initiated ATRP (SI-ATRP)	---	Thermo-responsiveness
Pennetreau <i>et al.</i> 2014 ¹⁶⁵	rGO, xanthate molecules	---	Radical covalent grafting	1 functional group per 35-70 carbon atoms	Dispersibility
Whitener <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹⁶⁶	Graphene and radical initiators	Chlorine radicals	Radical addition	---	Electrical conductivity

Au <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁶⁷	Few-layer graphene, sodium-naphthalide and Br for FLG-Br which <i>via</i> ATRP reacted with polymers	---	ATRP, Nucleophilic substitution	---	Improved dispersibility in acetone
Silvestrini <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁶⁸	Graphene, 4-methoxyaniline, and isopentyl nitrite	4-Methoxyphenyl radicals	Microfluidic reaction	---	Fluorescence properties
Ohno <i>et al.</i> 2019	GO, BPTA, TEA	---	ATRP	---	Liquid crystals
Edelthalhammer <i>et al.</i> 2020 ¹⁶⁹	Graphene and dibenzoylperoxide (DBPO)	Aryl radicals	Photo-cleavage of dibenzoylperoxide (DBPO) followed by radical addition	---	---
Garcia <i>et al.</i> 2022 ¹⁷⁰	GO, photoinitiator, and cysteamine	---	Thiol-ene radical addition	---	---
Bonanni <i>et al.</i> 2014 ¹⁷¹	Graphene oxide and Hydrazine monohydrate	---	Free radical Addition	---	Biosensing
Xia <i>et al.</i> 2017 ¹⁷²	GO Diselenide-containing molecules	---	Redox reaction and free-radical addition	---	Modulation of reactive oxygen species

Tunable magnetic properties at the nanoscale level are crucial to harvest the spintronic potential of carbon nanomaterials. *p*-Nitrophenyl-functionalization, followed by the epitaxial growth, led to a graphene system with ferromagnetic and antiferromagnetic order with perseverance up to 400 K.¹⁷³ At the same time, radical functionalization of graphene was found to substantially increase the number of unpaired local spins as indicated by the magneto transport studies. In another free-radical functionalization of graphene, its modification by cleaved AIBN in

NMP, resulted in the functionalization level of one isobutyronitrile group *per* 50 carbon atoms (Figure 14).¹⁶⁰

Figure 14 Synthetic route for graphene functionalization. Reproduced from the study by Zhang *et al.*¹⁶⁰ with permission. Copyright 2013 The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Such modifications allow for the prediction of alternative azo-radical initiators, bearing diverse functional groups, controlling the band gap energy and enhance the solubility of hybrid materials, hence, building up their high and multifunctional performance.

The enhanced and economic acid-base catalytic activities of the bifunctional hybrids in the one-pot deacetalization-nitroaldol reaction were observed for graphene bearing both organic amine and sulfonic acid groups – obtained *via* combined nucleophilic and radical addition¹⁶¹.

PE/GO composites were prepared from pentadecane-grafted rGO, employing dicumyl peroxide as a hydrogen abstractor to facilitate the radical addition of pentadecane to GO C=C bonds.¹⁶² Similarly, atom transfer radical addition (ATRA) allowed to anchor both low- and high-molecular-weight initiators onto the GO surface, furnishing macroinitiators for ATRP of various geometries: V-shape, hierarchical, and linear. The stability of polymer-grafted GO dispersions was found to be up to 80 days in organic solvents.¹⁶³ Poly(hexadecyl acrylate)-grafted GO was

Peroxides served as radical initiators in the functionalization of rGO by xanthates, while the highest xanthate grafting yield was observed for stoichiometric concentrations of seven different xanthates and three peroxides.¹⁶⁵ Peroxide grafting to the rGO surface was observed as a side reaction. Hence, bis-functionalized rGO, with a preserved graphene skeleton and improved dispersibility, was obtained in a one-step method.

In turn, hydrogenated graphene was found to have higher reactivities for chlorine and AIBN, as compared to pristine graphene, as dehydrogenation during consecutive functionalization promoted the formation of stable bonds between graphene and the radicals.¹⁶⁶ Exfoliated graphene functionalization via free radical addition of AIBN observed as a high yield method.¹⁶⁰

The dynamic covalent diselenide bond disrupts under both redox and visible light irradiation conditions. *In situ* covalent functionalization of GO was achieved by the reaction of GO and the stimuli-responsive diselenide bond.¹⁷² The redox reaction and free-radical addition were deduced as the GO functionalization mechanisms. Biocompatible diselenide polymer-modified GO di(tetraethylene glycol) diselenide was found to regulate the balance of reactive oxygen species (ROS). Selenium functionalized GO regulated the ROS concentration *via* the *in situ* generation of peroxide when ROS concentration is low and vice versa.

Brominated few-layer graphene (FLG-Br) is a convenient, stable in the liquid phase precursor that can be used to make a wide range of directly functionalized graphene. It was used to induce ATRP in order to produce FLG-PMMA (polymethyl methacrylate), which dispersibility in acetone was six times higher than for the controls.¹⁶⁷ The production of methoxy polyethylene glycol (mPEG)- and OH-substituted derivatives demonstrated that the FLG-Br must have been active in the nucleophilic substitution with the grafting ratios ranging from 6-25%.

Microfluidics was utilized to add aryl radicals – created *in situ via* the reaction of arylamines and isopentyl nitrite – to rGO flakes suspended in cyclohexyl-2-pyrrolidone.¹⁶⁸ The findings showed that shear stress in the reactor contributed to the chemistry of graphene materials by acting as a constant driving factor for the layered structures to be exfoliated.

In a new approach for the introduction of polymer brush onto GO surface, GO was modified with 2-((3-((2-bromo-2-methyl-propanol)oxypropylthioethylamine) hydrochloride,¹⁷⁴ i.e., a compound with an initiating group for ATRP and the amino group to react with the GO epoxy groups (**Figure 16**). The ATRP-initiator-functionalized GO yielded PMMA-grafted polymers with specified and narrow molecular weight distributions as lyotropic liquid crystals.

a)-

b)-

c)-

d)-

Figure 16 a)- ATRP fixation on GO; b)- synthesis of the ATRP bearing amino group; c)- AFM images of (a) BPTA-GO and (b) PMMA-GO; d)- Digital microscopy of polymer brush decorated GO: (a) PLMA-GO and (b)- PMMA-GO. Reproduced from the study by Ohno *et al.*¹⁷⁴ with permission. Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society.

Photo-cleavage of dibenzoyl peroxide (DBPO), followed by the optimization of radical addition to non-activated graphene, led to the controlled 2D-patterning of graphene facilitating the laser writing; exclusively covalent bonding to the laser-irradiated points was observed. The laser spot size and the mesh of the 'reading' map limited the differentiating resolution between two laser patterning spots to 2 mm. Those 'writing-and-reading' operations revealed that 2D graphene-patterning generated high-functionalization/addend regions.

A temperature-dependent Raman investigation (**Figure 17**) showed that thermal treatment could remove the graphene-based chemical information.¹⁶⁹

Figure 17 (a) Temperature-dependent Raman analysis of DBPO coated monolayer graphene; (b) D-band intensity evolution during functionalization (blue) and de-functionalization (red) over a temperature range from 0 to 450 °C, with a 532 nm laser, an integration time of 10 s, and an intensity of 0.88 mW. Reproduced from the study by Edelthalhammer *et al.*¹⁶⁹ with permission. Copyright 2020 The Authors, Published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

This behavior allowed for controlled functionalization, complete graphene structure restoration, and reusability for the storage of the new chemical information.

Thiolene radical addition (TERA) allowed to functionalize GO with reactive alkenes and thiols.¹⁷⁰ Cysteamine (CA)-functionalization of GO using TERA and Irgacure[®] 369 was studied. TERA preserved the GO chemistry allowing for various subsequent orthogonal reactions. As the cysteamine photoinitiator PI/CA ratio increased, PI-GO adducts were found. *N,N*-Dimethylamine benzyl radical (DBR) could displace alcohols and carboxylic acids and add to the electron-deficient double C–C bonds. Despite unfavorable conditions, TERA functionalized GO. By adjusting the PI/CA molar ratio, orthogonal GO functionalization was performed, reducing side

reactions. Additionally, carboxyl-grafting of graphene sheets enabled anchoring biomolecules *via* carbodiimide chemistry to further modulate the properties of GO.¹⁷¹

5.3 (2+1)-Cycloaddition

Graphene was covalently functionalized in a one-pot scheme *via* a nitrene (2+1)-cycloaddition under mild, controllable, and scalable conditions (**Figure 18**).¹⁷⁵

Figure 18 (2+1)-Cycloaddition of nitrene to rGO. Reproduced from the study by Faghani *et al.*¹⁷⁵ with permission. Copyright 2017 The Authors, Published by Wiley-VCH GmbH.

Chlorine substituents displayed varying reactivities on the functionalized graphene allowing for the post-modification. By gradual post-modification, functionalized graphene sheets were turned into specified 2D surfaces in high yields. This approach was beneficial allowing the production of bifunctional carbon nanomaterials with regulated ligand densities, and conjugation of sensitive bio(macro)molecules at room temperature. The studies related to the functionalization of 2D nanocarbons by (2+1)-cycloaddition are summarized in **Table 5**.

Table 5 Functionalization of 2D-nanocarbons via (2+1)-cycloaddition Reactions.

Ref.	Reactant	Degree of functionalization	Application
Soleimani <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁷⁶	GO-g-starch and di-alkyne PEG	0.301 anhydrous glucose unit per carbon atom of GO	Antibacterial activity
Faghani <i>et al.</i> 2017 ¹⁷⁵	Thermally rGO and 2-azido-4,6-dichloro-1,3,5-triazine	---	Multifunctional hybrid architectures
Guday <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁷⁷	Nanographene and Triazine functional groups	---	Electronic Properties
Tan <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁷⁸	Thermally rGO and triazine functionalized PEG	---	Antibacterial activity
Ujjain <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁷⁹	Graphene and Aryl Azide	---	Organic photovoltaics

Incubation of graphite in a dilute solution of sodium hypochlorite (NaClO) at 40 °C was reported as a top-down, one-pot, and gram-scale synthesis of high-quality graphene.¹⁷⁷ The resultant sheets comprised only 4 wt.% oxygen, which is practically equivalent to the oxygen content in graphene grown *via* CVD. Importantly, as authors claimed, the subsequent covalent functionalization *via* the nitrene (2+1)-cycloaddition preserved the π -conjugated system of graphene. Statistical analysis of data (**Figure 19**) from Raman spectroscopy and theoretically modeled XPS revealed a low number of sp^3 -carbon atoms, from 2 wt.% before to 4 wt.% after the covalent functionalization, while displaying the overall enhanced electroconductivity.

Figure 19 a) Raman spectra and theoretically calculated peaks of graphite starting material, nanographene (nG), and triazine-modified nG (nGTrz). The Hessian matrix was used to calculate phonon frequencies to calculate Raman intensities in the region of interest. Simulation of the Raman intensities was carried out applying the macroscopic dielectric tensor; b) I_D/I_G versus FWHM of 2D-band for nG and nGTrz; c) I_{2D}/I_G versus G-band wavenumber for nG and nGTrz; d) ω_{2D} versus ω_G for nG and nGTrz; e) Highly resolved C1s spectra with an inset of survey spectra (elemental percentages refer to the atomic percent, at.%) of nG and nGTrz; f) an expanded C K-edge NEXAFS spectrum. Reproduced from the study by Guday *et al.*¹⁷⁷ with permission.

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Theoretical studies and the observed doping effects pointed out that the sp^2 -hybridization for the carbon atoms participating in the (2+1)-cycloaddition might preserve the π -conjugated system while improving conductivity *via* n-type doping through the bridging *N*-atom. The elaborated protocols were indicated as scalable, and allowing for a gentle and effective approach to produce high-quality (nano)graphene.

Stepwise nucleophilic substitutions were used to convert a triazine-functionalized poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG-Trz) to a telechelic macromolecule with azide and hydroxyl functional groups.¹⁷⁸ The nitrene (2+1)-cycloaddition reaction was used to conjugate this macromolecule with graphene followed by a reaction with bromo-isobutyryl bromide to produce a 2D nanomaterial capable of initiating ATRP of acrylic monomers. *N*-Isopropyl acrylamide (NIPAM) was polymerized on the graphene surfaces, resulting in a 2D nanomaterial having the same joining point as graphene, PEG, and poly-NIPAM (PEG-G-PNIPAM) (**Figure 20**). Hydrophobic interactions emerged as the key mechanism describing graphene/bacteria interfaces, and therefore the enhanced antibacterial activity of such hybrids.

Figure 20 (A) IR spectra: (a) PEG, (b) PEG-Trz, (c) PEG-Trz-Ea, (d) PEG-Trz-Ea(N3), (e) PEG-G, (f) PEG-G-Bpb, and (g) PEG-G-PNIPAM. (B) ^1H NMR spectrum of PEG-G-PNIPAM (500 MHz, D_2O). (C) Raman spectra of TRGO, PEG-G, and PEG-G-PNIPAM. Reproduced from the study by Tan *et al.*¹⁷⁸ with permission. Copyright 2019 American Chemical Society.

Two *ortho*-substituted aryl azides were synthesized, each with a distinct aromatic ring and the ester/anhydride substituent.¹⁷⁹ Further, they underwent (2+1)-cycloaddition during thermolysis resulting in the production of an aziridine adduct with graphene sp^2 -carbon atoms. The resultant graphene sheets displayed dispersibility in both polar and non-polar liquids and revealed a high-level aryl functionalization of the graphene basal plane and edges *via* the aziridine linkage. Overall, this modification resulted in the formation of FLG. Poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT) and

f-graphene produced a homogenous composite with considerable photoluminescence quenching and better photostability. When compared to its pristine equivalent, bulk heterojunction (BHJ) of photovoltaic systems based on f-graphene doped P3HT: Phenyl-C₆₁-Butyric-Acid-Methyl Ester (PCBM) P3HT: PCBM showed a significantly better short circuit current density and a two-fold improvement in power conversion efficiency (**Figure 21**).

Figure 21 (a) & (b) Short Circuit Current (J_{sc}) (black line) and efficiency (blue line) versus concentration of f-graphenes (0, 1 & 5 wt.%), respectively, in the P3HT/PCBM (1:1) active layer of a photovoltaic cell. Reproduced from the study by Ujjain *et al.*¹⁷⁹ with permission. Copyright 2018 King Saud University.

Owing to the zero pyramidalization angle, graphene nanoplates (GNP) were anticipated to be less reactive in the (2+1)-nitrene cycloaddition.¹¹⁷ However, when the cycloaddition reaction of GNP with 4-(azidomethyl)benzoic acid (4-AMBA) was carried out with a support of microwave power (300 W) for 30 min at 160 °C, a combined TGA-XPS-FTIR analysis and decrease in the Raman I_D/I_G ratio revealed a major restoring of C-sp² hybridization in the f-GNP-4-AMBA, with a covalent functionalization at a level of 15 functional groups *per* 1000 carbon atoms.

5.4 (3+2)-Cycloaddition

Graphene was functionalized *via* 4-propargyl-oxybenzene-diazonium-tetrafluoroborate to facilitate the subsequent PEG attachment *via* (3+2)-azide-alkyne cycloaddition enabling water-dispersible graphene.¹⁸⁰ By customizing the functional groups on the diazonium moieties in the click-chemistry approaches, chemical changes can be attributed to graphene and the successive reactions to adhere to additional moieties are allowed, resulting in simple and adaptable routes for integrating graphene with a variety of matrices and sensed molecules. The studies related to functionalization of 2D-nanocarbons *via* cycloaddition reactions are summarized in **Table 6**.

Table 6 Functionalization of 2D-nanocarbons *via* cycloadditions.

Reference	Reactant	<i>In situ</i> produced reagent	Mechanism	Degree of functionalization	Applications
Folgado <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁸¹	Graphene coated Co/C nanoparticles and pyrene tagged dendrimers	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	---
Mishyn <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁸²	Graphene, 4-[(triisopropylsilyl)ethynyl]-benzene diazonium tetrafluoroborate	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Field-effect transistor
Neri <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁸³	Graphite, <i>N</i> -methyl benzoyl alanine and acetic anhydride	Münchnone	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Antimicrobial Activity
Basta <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁸⁴	Graphene/rGO and <i>N</i> -methylglycine and 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Dispersion Studies
Basta <i>et al.</i> 2022 ¹⁸⁵	Graphene flakes and <i>N</i> -methylglycine and 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	---
Ranishenka <i>et al.</i> 2021 ¹⁸⁶	GO and bicyclononyne-modified dyes	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Fluorescence Properties
Farquhar <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹⁸⁷	Anthranilic acid and Few layered Graphene	---	Diels-Alder cycloaddition	---	Electronic properties
Ferretti <i>et al.</i> 2022 ¹⁸⁸	Maleimide and partially/highly rGO (prGO/hrGO)	---	Diels-Alder cycloaddition	---	Compatibility of components in composites

Jin <i>et al.</i> 2011 ¹⁸⁰	Sodium bicarbonate, azido-dPEG4-acid solution and alkynyl-functionalized SP-graphene suspension		4-propargyloxybenzenediazonium and the subsequent 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition	---	Facilitation of further modifications
Ou <i>et al.</i> 2014 ¹⁸⁹	Polyaniline and amine-functionalized graphene	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Electrical conductivity
Uceta <i>et al.</i> 2019 ¹⁹⁰	FLG, chlorooximes, and Et ₃ N	Nitrile imine	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Modifications for nanoelectronics
Perez <i>et al.</i> 2017 ¹⁹¹	FLG, oDCB, formylcyanine, <i>N</i> -octylglycine	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	1 functional group per 171 carbon atoms	Electronic properties
Bekiarı <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁹²	Graphene covered slides, sarcosine, and 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde	Azomethine ylide	Solvolothermal 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition	---	Drug delivery
Ou <i>et al.</i> 2012 ¹⁹³	Phenol functionalized graphene, 2-bromoisobutyryl bromide and Et ₃ N	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	---
Barrejon <i>et al.</i> 2016 ¹⁹⁴	Graphene, hydrazones	Nitrile imine	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Modification of work function
Peng <i>et al.</i> 2013 ¹⁹⁵	Graphene and tetracyanoethylene oxide	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	---
Kaminska <i>et al.</i> 2013 ¹⁹⁶	GO/rGO, alkynyl terminated dopamine	---	Cu-catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition	---	Electronic properties
Ismail ¹⁹⁷	Alkyne-functionalized GO, azido decane, sodium ascorbate	---	Cu-catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition	---	Tribological properties
Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2012 ¹⁹⁸	rGO, PFTPA-CHO, <i>N</i> -methylglycine	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Bistable electrical switching
Castelain <i>et al.</i> 2012 ¹⁹⁹	GO functionalization via multiple routes	Diazonium salt	Cu-catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition	---	Electronic properties
Frolova <i>et al.</i> 2015 ²⁰⁰	Graphene and tetracyanoethylene oxide	Carbonyl ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	---
Namvari <i>et al.</i> 2014 ²⁰¹	GO reacted with NaN ₃ resulting GO-N ₃ , then with alkyne-glycoside	---	Cu-catalyzed 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition	---	---

Neri <i>et al.</i> 2015 ²⁰²	Graphene, 4-methyl-2-phenyl oxazolone/4-methyl-2- <i>p</i> -nitrophenyl oxazolone	Münchnone	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	2.1%-4.6%	---
Guo <i>et al.</i> 2020 ²⁰³	GO, chloroacetic acid and sodium hydroxide	---	Carboxylation of GO	---	Further modification by amidation or esterification
Tsoufis <i>et al.</i> 2015 ²⁰⁴	Exfoliated graphite solution, <i>N</i> -(hydroxyphenyl)glycine and paraformaldehyde	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Growth of iron oxide NPs on functionalized graphene
Zhao <i>et al.</i> 2015 ²⁰⁵	Graphene, 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde, and sarcosine	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Electronic properties
Georgitsopoulou <i>et al.</i> 2021 ²⁰⁶	GO, sarcosine and 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	70%	Drug delivery
Zhang <i>et al.</i> 2018 ¹⁵²	rGO, TPP, and sarcosine	---	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Optical properties
Wang <i>et al.</i> 2015 ²⁰⁷	Route 1: rGO, sarcosine, 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde, Route 2: rGO, sarcosine, and TPP 2	Diazonium compounds	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Optical properties
Silva <i>et al.</i> 2017 ²⁰⁸	Functionalized MWNTs/graphite and <i>N</i> -benzyloxycarbonylglycine	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	Biocompatible implant
Yin <i>et al.</i> 2017 ²⁰⁹	Graphene, sarcosine	---	(3+2)-cycloaddition	---	---
Cunha <i>et al.</i> 2018 ²¹⁰	GNP and iminodiacetic acid and paraformaldehyde	Azomethine ylide	1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition	---	---

Figure 22 summarizes different documented routes for the functionalization of graphene *via* this route.

Figure 22 (3+2)-Cycloaddition reactions for the functionalization of graphene: 1)-¹⁸⁰, 2)-¹⁸⁹, 3)-¹⁹⁰, 4)-¹⁹¹, 5)-¹⁹², 6)-¹⁹³, 7)-¹⁹⁴, 8)-¹⁹⁵.

Alkynyl chemistry serves the same purpose. Alkynyl-terminated dopamine interacts with graphene *via* π - π interactions and the resultant graphene can further be functionalized with ethenyl ferrocene *via* Cu(I)-catalyzed (3+2)-cycloaddition reaction.¹⁹⁶ The same click coupling approach led to highly oil-soluble triazole ring-bearing graphene sheets.¹⁹⁷ (3+2)-Cycloaddition of azomethine ylide yielded a solution-processable, PFTPA (perfluorotri-*n*-butylamine) covalently grafted r-GO (RGO-PFTPA). The switch-on voltage for the as-fabricated device was ca. -1.4 V, and the ON/OFF-state current ratio was greater than 10^3 . A high positive voltage threshold stands for the

reversible ON-OFF transition process. Accessibility and stability of both the OFF and ON states under constant voltage and pulse voltage stress of -1 V for up to 3 h and one hundred million continuous read cycles are evident from **Figure 23**.²¹¹

Figure 23 A)- PFTPA_CHO and RGO-PFTPA synthesis B)- Current Density Voltage² (J-V) (a): stability in ON, OFF stage, (b)- under stress of -1 V, and (c)- under read pulse with peak voltage of -1 V, pulse width was $1 \mu\text{s}$ and pulse period was $2 \mu\text{s}$. Reproduced from the study by Zhang *et al.*²¹¹ with permission. Copyright 2011 Wiley Periodicals, Inc.

Cu(I)-catalyzed Huisgen (3+2)-cycloaddition of azides and alkynes is a versatile tool for the synthesis of novel materials. Owing to its modular nature, fast reaction time, relatively high reactivity, selectivity, and predictability, this reaction is essential in organic synthesis. The reaction between alkyne-modified graphene and an azide-functionalized polymer resulted in graphene flakes covalently modified with a conjugated polymer, poly[(9,9-dihexylfluorene)-*co-alt*-(9,9-bis-(6-azidohexyl)fluorene)].¹⁹⁹ This diazonium method, contrarily, avoids using a silane-protected alkyne and streamlines the technique by removing the redundant protection/deprotection steps.

(3+2)-Cycloaddition was used to covalently functionalize graphene with phenol groups without affecting its electrical properties.¹⁹³ These phenol moieties on the functionalized graphene sheets were then derivatized using 2-bromoisobutyryl bromide leading to the adherence of ATRP initiators and the subsequent anchoring PMMA.

Graphene-tetracyanoethylene oxide TCNEO, a new type of functionalized graphene, was also synthesized using the (3+2)-cycloaddition.¹⁹⁵ The degree of functionalization was estimated to be around 1 TCNEO group per 85 carbon atoms. Upon heating up to 100 °C, TCNEO undergoes a ring opening and the formation of carbonyl ylide which is attached to graphene *via* (3+2)-cycloaddition.²⁰⁰

Mono- and disaccharides were also grafted on the edges and planes of GO *via* azide and terminal alkyne Cu(I)-catalyzed Huisgen (3+2)-cycloaddition.²⁰¹ GO reaction with sodium azide, followed by the attack of alkyne-modified maltose, mannose, galactose, and glucose, introduced azide and 1,3-diazidepropan-2-ol, respectively to the edges of graphene. Glycoside-grafted graphene displayed enhanced water dispersion and stability of up to two weeks. **Figure 24** summarizes the (3+2)-cycloaddition functionalization routes for the rGO sheets.

Figure 24 (3+2)-Cycloaddition reaction for functionalization of reduced graphene as reported by Ismail *et al.* (B)¹⁹⁷ and Namvari *et al.* (A&C).²⁰¹

(3+2)-Cycloaddition was also employed to add phenol groups to graphene keeping the electrical properties intact. Two hydroxyl groups could be then added to graphene in a single process. For aniline graft polymerization, phenol-derivatized graphene was treated with aminopropyltriethoxysilane to generate a dense aminopropyl silane self-assembled monolayer containing active sites for the polymerization.¹⁸⁹ *In situ* polymerization of aniline monomer, in the presence of ammonium peroxydisulfate under acidic conditions, formed the conductive polyaniline (PANI) layer on self-assembled monolayer-coated graphene. This reaction proved to be exceptionally efficient for the formation of homogenous conductive PANI (14.5 wt.%)–graphene hybrid composites, at ambient temperature and short reaction times (24 h). Another (3+2)-cycloaddition

was performed by reacting a solid mixture of graphite flakes and mesoionic oxazolones at 70-120 °C. The process was evaluated using two oxazolones of different substitutions, and both substrates showed a significant degree of functionalization (2.1–4.6 % estimated in terms of weight loss by TGA when heated from 100 °C to 700 °C). Theoretical calculations revealed that the (3+2)-cycloaddition could occur *via* a concerted process as well as a stepwise mechanism including a zwitterionic intermediate. The irreversible decarboxylation that occurs in the final stage explains the high degree of functionalization that has been observed experimentally, and it is the driving force behind the process.²⁰² However, carboxylation was not proved to be an efficient modification for GO functionalization as well as for the possibility of double functionalization *via* further modifications.²⁰³

To perform CuI-catalyzed (3+2)-cycloaddition click chemistry, highly dispersed Cu NPs were immobilized on carbon nanomaterials (CNMs; graphene/CNTs) employed as recyclable and reusable catalysts. CNMs containing immobilized *N*-heterocyclic carbene (NHC)-Cu complexes – made from an imidazolium-based carbene and CuI – exhibited an outstanding stability and efficiency even at modest catalyst loadings.²¹² The graphene-supported catalyst outperformed the CNT-supported catalyst in terms of catalytic activity, with considerably more than 10 cycles of reuse and relatively minor activity loss, far outperforming currently available supported Cu catalysts for the click reactions. Such catalysts could serve as the foundation for future nanocomposites with intrinsic restorable capabilities, and catalytic activity, displaying also self-healing qualities.

Fe₃O₄ NPs were generated on the graphene surface through direct liquid-phase exfoliation of highly crystalline graphite (without any oxidation treatment) and the subsequent (3+2)-cycloaddition.²⁰⁴ The resultant graphene derivatives were used in a modified wet-impregnation

approach to immobilize the nanoparticle precursor (Fe cations) at the inserted organic groups, followed by contact with acetic acid vapors. Heating (calcination), under an inert atmosphere, produced the ultimate graphene-Fe₃O₄ hybrid material. The hybrid material exhibited superparamagnetic behavior attributed to the prevalence of iron oxide NPs.

G-OH (2-(3,4-dihydroxy phenyl) pyrrolidine grafted graphene), a GO alternative, is a flexible substrate for manufacturing graphene-derived products.²⁰⁵ Magnetic G-FeCl₃ (graphene-FeCl₃ complex), G-PR (resin functionalized graphene), G-EP (epoxide functionalized graphene), and G-MA (methacryloyl functionalized graphene) were synthesized from G-OH. Owing to the controllable (3+2)-cycloaddition, G-OH and its derivatives had a nearly identical electrical structure and characteristics that of the pristine graphene. This process can be easily adapted to additional reactive graphene derivative platforms, allowing a wide range of functional chemistries to be produced and broadening the scope of graphene practical applications.

To obtain nanohybrid RGO-5-[4-(2-bromoethoxy) phenyl]-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin (RGO-TPP 1), rGO was functionalized by reaction with sarcosine and 4-hydroxybenzaldehyde followed by the nucleophilic substitution with selected porphyrin (**Figure 25**).

Figure 25 Summary of (3+2)-cycloaddition reactions employed for the functionalization of graphene from references 1²⁰⁶, 2¹⁹⁶, 3²¹³.

Despite the cost-effectiveness and single-step grafting of OH groups to the surface of rGO, controllable OH-addition was not possible *via* this route. The same study designed formyl containing RGO-5-[4-(2-(4-formylphenoxy)ethoxy)-phenyl]-10,15,20-triphenylporphyrin (RGO-TPP 2) *via* the formation of azomethine ylide.²⁰⁷ As a result, both hybrids were characterized by improved optoelectronic (OL) performance indicating a synergy derived from the covalent bonds. The approach to adaptable nanoconjugates with upgraded properties opens the pathway to more innovative chemical and optoelectronic systems. FLG functionalized *via* (3+2)-

cycloaddition of heptamethine cyanine, with a substantial absorption in the NIR region, was also treated as a potential candidate for multiple optoelectronic applications.¹⁹¹ Another study reported the synthesis of an RGO-TPP nanohybrid of enhanced nonlinear optical absorption properties.²¹³

(3+2)-Cycloaddition enabled NP exfoliation for the covalent functionalization of graphene nanoflakes (GF) employed to create free-standing, still hydrophobic films by layer-by-layer deposition of chitosan (CHI), alginate (ALG), and graphene.²⁰⁸ Despite preserved thermal stability, an increase in the storage modulus and dynamic mechanical response of graphene-incorporated films were observed at 1 Hz and 37 °C. Also, alkylated Percec monodendron having three long alkyl chains (3,4,5-trioctadecyloxybenzaldehyde)-aided liquid phase exfoliation was employed for the production of graphene dispersions opening a new route for the engineered graphene²⁰⁹. Also, a solvothermal technique was employed as an alternative to the (3+2)-cycloaddition of azomethine ylides.¹⁹² Glass deposition of graphene nanosheets aided the asymmetrical reaction, and one-side functionalization produced amphiphilic nanosheets with catechol groups, leaving the unmodified side hydrophobic, hence making the Janus-type graphene. Those water-dispersed amphiphilic graphene nanosheets were self-organized into bilayer superstructures with a hydrophilic exterior and a hydrophobic interior. The latter could be employed in drug delivery systems and host hydrophobic compounds like anticancer medications. Indeed, camptothecin, a water-insoluble drug, was employed as an example to demonstrate how it may be transported to the water phase utilizing graphene as a transporter. Furthermore, paraformaldehyde and iminodiacetic acid were used for GNP functionalization *via* solvent-free (3+2)-cycloaddition.²¹⁰ The temperature range from 180 to 250 °C was found to favor functionalization, while the range from 220 to 250 °C enhanced the loss of dicarboxylic groups, hence also losing the functionality of the material. GO nanosheets were also biofunctionalized utilizing azido-starch.¹⁷⁶ The residual azido groups were

also used to cross-link biofunctionalized GO with dialkyne PEG. As anticipated, the synthetic GO hydrogel removed methylene blue efficiently. Attributable to the biocompatibility of its elements (PEG and starch), the hydrogel had also potential in biomedical applications like drug delivery systems. Its antibacterial properties are likely due to the formation of triazole rings during the click reaction.

(3+2)-Cycloaddition of nitrile *N*-oxides generated *in-situ* from triethylamine and *N*-chloroimines (obtained *via* dehydrohalogenation of chlorinated oximes) to graphene was performed in the presence of microwaves. Computational studies indicated a rather slow reaction progress relative to prior graphene cycloadditions while MW irradiation speeded up the reaction.¹⁹⁰

Employing π - π stacking and with an expectation of surface interactions between pyrene and MNPs (magnetic NPs), dendrimers with a pyrene moiety were chosen as spacers between the MNP graphene surface and PVDF chains.¹⁸¹ Pyrene-tagged spacer-11 with ten acetylenic functional groups was effectively synthesized followed by grafting of azido functionalized PVDF chains *via* Huisgen (3+2)-cycloadditions onto each dendrimer branch. Fluorescence studies of MNP-dendrimer constructs showed that the non-covalent interactions (and hence grafting) were largely reversible upon heating. This novel feature might allow for the future applications of hybrid MNPs in thermos responsive materials integrating magnetic capabilities with PVDF for high-tech applications.

An interdigitated gold electrode-based generic platform for biosensing applications made it possible to form a field-effect transistor by the electrochemical grafting of the graphene channel with aryl diazonium species.¹⁸² Monolayer graphene deposition was achieved by electrochemical grafting of a protected ethynyl phenyl diazonium. The graphene channel controlled covalent functionalization resulted in hole and electron charge mobilities of 1739 ± 376 and 1698 ± 536

$\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively, permitting their use as (bio)sensors. In turn, mesoionic oxazolium *N*-oxides displaying azomethine ylide characteristics are called münchnones and react with acetylenic dipolarophiles to form pyrrole derivatives. Indeed, (3+2)-cycloaddition was applied to make FLG-containing pyrrole rings.¹⁸³ By using diazonium chemistry, benzene thiol groups were grafted onto münchnone-graphene surfaces to attach Ag-NPs and Nisin – an antimicrobial peptide. The synthesis of münchnone-functionalized graphene with Nisin@Ag enhanced the overall processability and the resultant G-MuSH/Nisin@Ag nanocomposite was evaluated as a potential new antibacterial nanomaterial.

Optimization of the 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition can yield highly functionalized GO, and a reaction of GO with a substantial excess of the functionalizing agent can give a high density of out-of-plane groups on the graphene surface.²⁰⁶ For instance, the mass ratio between GO and the two organic reactants including 3,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde and sarcosine was altered to 1:30 while the heating was prolonged to one week. Under these conditions, densely functionalized insulating GO was produced, unlike the reaction using a 1:10 ratio of reactants. Component analysis as displayed in (**Figure 26**) proved a high degree of functionalization as the concentration of sp^3 -carbon and oxygen/nitrogen-bonded carbon was higher than the concentration of aromatic carbon atoms.

Figure 26 a) XPS spectrum of GO-ff-OH with elemental analysis; b) deconvoluted high-resolution XPS on C1s region and, c) respective component analysis. Reproduced from the study by Georgitsopoulou²⁰⁶ with permission. Copyright 2021 Elsevier.

Graphene grafted with 2-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl) pyrrolidine (DHPP) via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of *in-situ* generated azomethine ylide. Graphene-DHPP used as starting material for further functionalization.²⁰⁵

A class of heterogeneous, recyclable Cu(II)-bis-cyclen intercalated GO complex was produced by easy, non-covalent intercalation and found to be an effective catalyst for the CuAAC (Cu-catalyzed azide–alkyne cycloaddition) process to isolate 1,4-disubstituted-1,2,3-triazoles in good yield (89%).²¹⁴ Concerning kinetics, (3+2)-dipolar cycloaddition of nitrile imines to graphene was found to be slow while significantly accelerated by MW irradiation,¹⁹⁴ and further by applying solvents and exfoliation techniques of higher NP-individualizing power.¹⁸⁴

Also, defect engineering of monolayer graphene *via* low-energy electron beam enhanced the chemical reactivity towards further covalent functionalization processes.¹⁸⁵ For the quantification of surface load and sustainability of epoxy groups induced *via* epoxy-amine reaction, the functionalized GO was immobilized on a glass support. Covalent attachment of one epoxy group per nm² was achieved *via* this reaction and most of the functional groups displayed enhanced

sustainability after reduction which promoted further azide group functionalization and suppressed aggregation extent.¹⁸⁶

5.5 (4+2)-Cycloaddition

Diels-Alder cycloaddition of arynes was frequently employed as the covalent modification of FLG.¹⁸⁷ For instance, anthranilic acid was used for the aryne precursor (*via* thermal loss of N₂ and CO₂). Similarly, rGOs of lower and higher O-content were functionalized *via* Diels-Alder reaction with maleimide, and the reaction was studied both theoretically and experimentally.¹⁸⁸ Here, rGO was synthesized by thermal treatment of dry GO powder at 350 °C toward a partial reduction under air flux; for the production of highly reduced GO production, thermal treatment at 1100 °C under argon flux was performed. Theoretical studies proved exothermic reactions more favorable than the non-covalent functionalization strategies for r-GO. Small or no reaction barrier of oxygen functionalized sites of GO for maleimide DA reaction highlighted them as more reactive than the defect-free sites.

Furthermore, theoretical evaluation of solvent and temperature effects led to higher enthalpies. Maleimide functionalized r-GO was also found to have a tunable bandgap making it a potential candidate for nanoelectronics applications.

6 Conclusions and outlook

In the last dozen years, a significant progress has been made in the covalent functionalization of carbon nanoallotropes. From the mechanistic point-of-view, covalent functionalization of 1D and 2D sp²-carbon nanoallotropes covers radical, electrophilic, and nucleophilic addition as well as cycloaddition – typically changing carbon atom hybridization from sp² to sp³, with a minimal

chance of leaving the sp^2 -carbon atoms intact. Researchers have developed novel chemical strategies, proceeding in all of the states of matter, and new materials that have improved their properties and applications with pristine/non-modified nanocarbons as the ‘negative references’. One of the key challenges in the functionalization of carbon nanoallotropes was, and in fact still is, achieving precise, atomic-level control over the functionalization process. The position, density, and operating functionality of the functional groups on the surface of carbon nanoallotropes significantly affect their properties and potential applications. To address this challenge, various approaches have been explored, including the use of molecular templates, self-assembling, and reactive intermediates. The development of new techniques for the precise control of the functionalization process will be without a doubt the milestone in the nearest future.

The other still valid challenge is the long-term stability of functionalized carbon nanoallotropes – both the free-standing and embedded ones – in a variety of matrices and coatings. The presence of functional groups on the surface of these materials can lead to degradation over time, limiting their applicability. Researchers have explored different approaches, such as encapsulation or the use of protective layers, to improve the long-term stability of functionalized carbon nanoallotropes. This is a crucial area of research as it directly affects the reliability and durability of the materials in the daily-life applications.

The primary target of functionalizing carbon nanoallotropes is always to design and synthesize materials with specific properties for the well-defined applications. The development of new techniques for the precise control of functionalization processes and the tailoring of the electronic and optical properties of the pre-designed materials will be key areas of research. It is difficult to estimate the time required to achieve these goals, as the development of new materials and techniques is a complex and iterative process. However, continued investment in research and

development is crucial to overcoming the challenges associated with the functionalized carbon nanoallotropes. Particularly, the ‘from functionalization to functionality’ approach should focus on the covalent transformations not compromising the target high-performance of the nanocarbon-based implementation schemes.

In conclusion, the covalent functionalization of carbon nanoallotropes is a promising field with an immense potential for various applications. Chemists and nanotechnologists have made a significant progress in this field over the last dozen years, but challenges remain. The scientific society needs to address them to achieve the goals, including precise control over functionalization processes, long-term stability, and tailoring of electronic and optical properties.

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